

standICT.eu 2026

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

FOLLOWING THE FELLOWS

**IMPACT REPORT FROM
FUNDED APPLICANTS TO
THE STANDICT.EU 2026
FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME**

FOURTH OPEN CALL

Editors:

Silvana Muscella, Mona Marill,
Maria Giuffrida, Gabriele Quattrocchi,
Nathaniel Cueter, Teresa Ridolfi

Disclaimer

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About StandICT.eu

The project is coordinated by [Trust-IT Srl](#) (IT) acting as a technical coordinator, and [Dublin City University](#) (IE) acting as financial coordinator, supported by its partners [AUSTRALO](#) (ES), [European Digital SME Alliance](#) (BE), [Fraunhofer](#) (DE) and [Open Forum Europe](#) (BE).

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■ Foreword

The European Green Deal & the New Industrial Strategy for Europe call for a strong EU presence in international Standardisation development. The recent significant shifts in the geopolitical environment call for increasing the intensity of the EU presence in international standardisation committees. Building up a strong and sustainable pool of European Standardisation competent professionals who are ready to engage in European and International Standardisation is crucial. With this we are pleased to contribute to this already engaged community through the “Following the Fellows” series Impact Reports, now in its fourth edition under the new StandICT.eu 2026 project, continuing the work of the precursor edition, proving a tangible testimony of the impact generated by European ICT experts working in collaboration with international Standardisation Developing Organisations (SDOs), thanks to the financial support provided through the StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship Programme, as paramount part of the broader mission of the StandICT.eu 2026 Coordination and Support Action.

The main purpose of these regular publications is to display the work carried out by our fellows and illustrate the demonstrable outcomes that excellent research can make to both society and to the economy (SMEs or industry at large). Therefore, we attempt to substantiate how each effort on which the fellows are engaged provides a potential benefit to society and contributes to the achievement of specific, desired, societal outcomes because of the ICT Standardisation efforts.

As we move forward, our commitment to bolstering the EU’s role in international standardisation remains strong. The “Following the Fellows” series is not only a testament to the achievements of our fellows but also serves as an inspiration and a call to action for future standardisation professionals. By highlighting the critical work of these individuals, we aim to underscore the importance of ICT standardisation in driving innovation, ensuring competitive advantages, and contributing to the sustainability and resilience of society and the economy at large.

We invite the standardisation community, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and all interested parties to engage with the insights and findings presented in these reports.

Silvana Muscella

StandICT.eu 2026 Project Coordinator
& CEO, Trust-IT Srl

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■ Introduction

This report marks the fourth batch of funded fellows under the StandICT.eu 2026 Programme. It shares perspectives and the first results of the fellowships that were funded under this fourth open call¹.

Our team is delighted to showcase the fourth series of StandICT.eu 2026 fellowship stories of the funded experts detailing the addressed standards and landscapes how these will fill in the identified gaps and impact the related stakeholders and society. The results obtained by our fellows fully respond to many of the objectives set out in the EU Strategy on Standardisation. They mainly prioritise and address standardisation needs in strategic ICT areas, enhance European leadership in global standards, support innovation and improve the overall integrity of the European standardisation system.

Standards are at the core of the EU Single Market and global competitiveness and play a fundamental (even if sometimes invisible) function in our daily lives. They can ensure the interoperability of products and services, reduce costs, improve safety, and foster innovation.

At the same time, standards act as powerful drivers for innovation and growth by helping researchers bring their innovation to the market and spread technological advances, as standards make their results transparent and ensure high quality. One of the key purposes of StandICT.eu 2026 is to support the activity of European ICT experts to contribute to the modernisation and consolidation of the European standardisation system as well as to the valorisation of their research outputs, with a view to efficiently respond to the EU's ambitions towards different thematic ICT areas, such as such as Metaverse and Digital Product Passport, which were the focus of the announcement of the 4th Open Call.

The primary purpose of this document is to share the results attained through the work carried out by the funded experts and to showcase the most relevant outcomes, creating awareness of the potential impact and repercussions of such impact on commerce, industry, governmental policies and strategies and the society. This open call is the fourth out of nine StandICT.eu 2026 Open Calls. Each open call will have a dedicated impact report demonstrating the key findings, contributions, and observations with the StandICT.eu community, the European Commission, the Multi-Stakeholder Platform for ICT Standardisation, the SDOs, and even beyond, all interested actors of our ever-growing StandICT.eu community.

In this funding batch, **in total, 40 fellowships** were granted, tackling the five policy areas as defined in the ICT Standardisation Rolling Plan 2024²:

- ▶ **Foundational drivers: 10 fellowships** focusing on Cybersecurity Network and Information Security (8 fellowships), and Data Economy (2).
- ▶ **Key enablers and security: 23 fellowships** focusing on Artificial Intelligence (10 fellowships), 5G/6G (3), electronic identification (4), Internet of Things (3), Quantum technology (2) and Cloud and edge computing (1).
- ▶ **Innovation for Digital Single Market: 1 fellowship** focusing on Blockchain and DLT.
- ▶ **Sustainable growth: 6 fellowships** focusing on Construction Building Information Modelling, Circular Economy Including Digital Product Passport, ICT Environmental Impact, Robotics and Autonomous Systems, Digitisation Of European Industry and Smart Cities.

During this funding round, no fellowship addressed **societal challenges**.

1 <https://www.standict.eu/standicteu-2026-4th-open-call>

2 <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/rolling-plan-2024>

Overview of the Open Call #4

The fourth open call was running from the 12th of February until the 12th of April 2024. It received 104 applications out of which 40 were selected for funding, with an overall 343,024 Euro granted.

The StandICT.eu Open Calls target European ICT standardisation experts contributing to the international SDOs, work groups and/ or technical committees at any of the priority topics, as taken from the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation. Due to their current strategic importance at the EU level, applications focusing on the topics of Metaverse and Digital Product Passport are highly encouraged. However, this open call was completely open for applications tackling a broad range of ICT domains (as encompassed in the ICT Rolling Plan for Standardisation) and treated as equally valid.

Fellowship Profiles

The funded applications offer a large geographic spectrum with 14 different EU or associated countries (with most experts from Belgium, France, Italy, and Austria). 25% of the funded experts are female, reflecting the wider context of ICT professionals where the majority of the workers are male. Moreover, 30% of the funded fellows are new to the StandICT.eu programme, and the remainder are returning fellows who have already benefited from a funded StandICT.eu fellowship.

The retained fellowships are represented with a balance across the key technologies, and with a wide spectrum of SDOs that will benefit from the competence and expertise of the applicants. As outlined in the figure here below, a large portion of the granted fellows have chosen their focus across a varied range of horizontal and vertical ICT areas; the most popular areas in this batch include artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and electronic identification. Moreover, this funding batch is marked by a great variety of vertical ICT areas covered by the fellowships, namely quantum technology and data economy.

Figure 1 - Overview of the #4 Open Call key results and insights

Engaged SDOs, Organisations and European Projects

65% of the fellows' activity contributes to the activities of Committees or Working Groups operating in global SDOs including ISO/IEC, IEEE, IETF, ISO 3GPP, W3C ERCIM, and IEC while the remainder works with European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), covering ETSI, CEN, CEN/CENELEC. Finally, 16 European funded and innovation research projects (see Table 1) are related to the engaged work in the OC#4 fellowships, focusing on different horizontal and vertical technologies.

Table 1 – EU Projects related to OC#4 Fellowships

Project name	ICT Area	Funding Programme	Related StandICT.eu Fellows
ACCRA EU	eHealth	Horizon2020	Amelie Gyrard
SOLARIS	eGovernance	HorizonEurope	Piercosma Bisconti Lucidi
LUCIA	eHealth	HorizonEurope	
AI4HOPE		HorizonEurope	
SYNTHEMA		HorizonEurope	
EBSI-VECTOR	Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies	DEP	Markus Sabadello
EBSI-TRACE4EU			
CircThread	Circular Economy	Horizon2020	Rembrandt Koppelaar
CIRPASS-2	Digital Product Passport	DEP	
CE-RISE	Circular Economy	Horizon2020	
6GSANDBOX	6G	HorizonEurope	David Artuñedo Guillén
TEF-Health	eHealth	HorizonEurope	João Manuel Leitão Quintas
FaceRehab		AAL	
ORACIA			
ROSIA		Horizon2020	
Lifebots		Horizon2020	

Now, we are delighted to share with you the insights from our granted fellows' work – and we truly hope that these results encourage you to get involved in our StandICT.eu community and join our Fellowship Programme under our forthcoming Open Calls, the European Observatory for ICT Standards (EUOS) - via the Technical Working Groups (TWGs) delivering up-to-date landscape and gap analysis, and finally Standards Academy training future experts in ICT Standardisation.

Together, we shape and reinforce the European and international ICT standardisation arena!

1.

Foundational Drivers

■ Upgrading prEN 18037 to final stage

Elzbieta Andrukiewicz

*Project Leader, National Institute of Telecommunications
Poland*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC13 WG3 Security evaluation and assessment

Role

Project leader

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Cybersecurity certification is one of the top priorities set up in the EU digital strategy. It is included in respective EU legislations such as the Cybersecurity Act or NIS2 Directive.

The Cybersecurity Act requests the European Commission to develop and maintain the Union Rolling Working Programme (URWP), which is used to identify potential needs for cybersecurity certification and plan long-term initiatives toward the creation of appropriate cybersecurity certification schemes. The first URWP was published on February 7th, 2024.

The conclusion of URWP, section 4, reads: "The Framework [defined in CSA] should constitute a flexible tool with procedures that can adapt to products, services, or processes that face specific challenges and needs in terms of cybersecurity assurance."

Clearly, there is a need to provide such a flexible tool. The challenge is to create a widely recognised standard (European or international) that could provide the tool that will help implement new certification schemes in a unified and complementary way. There are no such standards on the market.

With this fellowship, I contribute to creating the European Standard 18037, "Guidelines on Sectoral Cybersecurity Assessment," which can fill this gap. The objective is to provide a consistent methodology for assessing cybersecurity requirements based on the risk of the intended use of the object of evaluation/certification. Appropriate security objectives and security requirements that reflect risk levels can be formulated and implemented. Further, a unified method of defining assurance requirements based on the concept of attack potential is provided.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship contributes to obtaining a common view on security requirements expressed by various stakeholders which can be addressed by certification tools and on assurance requirements, which could allow the re-use evaluation results obtained in various certification schemes.

The concept of EN 18037 is based on two leading standards, ISO/IEC 15408 series and ISO/IEC 27005. Additionally, the standard adopts the concept of attack potential specified in ISO/IEC 18045 with a similar market-driven approach known as Cyberthreat Intelligence (CTI).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

A unified approach to developing cybersecurity certification schemes and the possibility of reusing evaluation results produced under different certification schemes would be a dominant factor in decreasing the costs and workload needed for the certification of composite products or services. This could, at least partly, remove financial barriers for SMEs to enter the certification market.

Impact on Society

The CSA facilitates the use of certification as a powerful cybersecurity measure that can be implemented without additional burdens among Member States. Typically in the past, the product or service had been certified, and then again, it was subject to similar certification procedure if specific requirements regarding certification took place in another country. Once the European Cybersecurity Certification scheme enters effect (based on relevant Implementing Act), all certificates, issued under such a scheme, will be recognized by law in every Member State.

The landscape the CSA deals with encompasses schemes that are currently in operation e.g., SOG-IS MRA that consists of several national cybersecurity certification schemes providing certificates in compliance with Common Criteria and being now under transposition to EUCC, or set of schemes dedicated to the telecommunication market, and offered by the GSMA. However, new potential candidate schemes for key industry verticals such as IoT, cloud, communications, payments, automotive will emerge.

The project I am working on could facilitate coordinated and consistent implementations of different cybersecurity certification schemes that operate under the CSA framework. Specifically, it relates to common understanding and implementations of the assurance requirements across different schemes based on the common reference model proposed in the standard. In that way cost- and time-effective implementations would be possible in the future. The societal impact measured by increasing confidence in the certification as a powerful cybersecurity tool would be real.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute in developing a new standard EN 18037 "Guidelines on Sectoral Cybersecurity Assessment".

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

My application aims to create a European Standard (EN), which includes essentially the following documents: the preliminary and final Disposition of Comments and the final draft of the standard.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The standard is on the final stage requiring the Formal Vote only. At the Enquire stage, the draft has received 100% "Yes" votes although several issues had to be resolved to improve the quality of the content. EN 18037 is waiting for the formal opening of the ballot.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2307986&cs=1BFE244DDA2A68D1B5C93795034A8DD05

Guidance (ISO 19770-10) for implementing IT asset management

Stéphane Joret

*Senior expert consultant in ITSM and ITAM, Liscience
France*

Sector

Data Economy

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO JTC1 / SC7 Software and systems engineering WG21 Information technology asset management

Role

Editor of ISO 19770-10

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship contributed to the drafting of ISO/IEC CD TS 19770-10 the Part 10: Guidance for implementing ITAM.

Regarding ISO 19770-10 edition 1, the priorities are the following:

- ▶ Collect the comments raised by national standardisation bodies in the 2nd ballot after they are consolidated by ISO.
- ▶ Write draft disposition to address received comments and change requests.
- ▶ Review of draft disposition with the study group for ISO 19770-10 and with the members of ISO JTC1 / SC7 / WG21 before the plenary in Berlin.
- ▶ Interactively finalise and review the disposition of comments in work sessions with participants at the plenary in Berlin.
- ▶ Deliver to ISO the finalised disposition of comments and the updated new draft of ISO 19770-10 edition 1.

In parallel, I aim to initiate the scope of work for ISO 19770-10 edition 2 to maintain the alignment with other ISO 19770 on-going projects and to improve the added value of ISO 19770-10.

Moreover, the main challenges concern enrolling volunteers to work on the project with me. Also, understanding how to work in international standardisation committees is vital, which implies going beyond IT asset management microcosm to deliver more value to related disciplines such as cybersecurity or sustainability. Finally, this work has to deal with a very particular comment raised by the Chinese standardisation body.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My funded application directly contributes to ISO 19770 family of standards because it is a guide for their practical implementation. There is a real need for such guidance (AFNOR, the French national standardisation body, tried to address it in 2013 with GA Z67-215) as IT asset management implementation is very complex due to its deep integration with other disciplines such as cybersecurity, finance, corporate asset management, procurement, service management or sustainability.

Therefore, my fellowship also contributes to related families of standards such as ISO 27000, ISO 55000, ISO 20000 and ISO 14001. With ISO 19770-10 edition 1, this contribution is indirect, but my vision is to develop a direct contribution with edition 2.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

ISO 19770-10 target audience is organisations that want to improve their IT asset management. This includes SMEs such as practitioners and improvers in public and private organisations, ITAM consultants, ITAM trainers and training providers.

Impact on Society

Simplified ITAM adoption, thanks to practical guidance and appropriate skill development, can financially benefit all European public and private organisations, reduce the European impact of ICT on the environment, and reduce economic and technological dependence on non-European companies. The impact can be huge, as IT assets are everywhere, notably with a growing presence in the industry. Trustworthy data about IT assets is a key enabler for IT security that is now crucial in the context of hybrid war at the European eastern border.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to editing the following standards:

- ▷ ISO 19770-10 edition 1 and ISO 19770-10 edition 2
- ▷ ISO 19770-13 edition 1 about sustainability in IT asset management
- ▷ ISO 19770-5 edition 3 providing an overview of ISO 19770 family of standards

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

My fellowship with result in the following two key deliverables:

- ▷ ISO 19770-10 edition 1 as a Technical Specification, with expected publication by the end of 2024, schedule depending on work progression with the ISO editor (Yvonne CHEN) after the last Technical Committee draft is provided to the SC7/WG21 convenor (done end of May 2024).
- ▷ Scope of work for ISO 19770-10 edition 2.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The last Committee Draft of ISO 19770-10 edition 1 has been provided to the SC7/WG21 convenor (Ron BRILL) with the related disposal of comments raised by national bodies in the second ballot. My input to the scope of work for ISO 19770-10 edition 2 has been interactively revised 4 with attendants at the plenary meeting in Berlin. The scope of work for edition 2 has been initiated with the principles of working and the change backlog, including their origin, idea, and contributors.

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://www.iso.org/standard/86588.html>

<https://genorma.com/en/standards/iso-iec-cd-ts-19770-10>

<https://www.softwareone.com/en/blog/articles/2022/11/14/iso19770-10-implementing-an-itam-best-practice-framework>

Integrating architecture, interoperability, cross-cutting aspects and AI standards in data spaces

Antonio Kung

CEO, Trialog

France

Sector

Data Economy

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC7 software and system engineering

ISO/IEC JTC1/WG13 trustworthiness

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41 IoT and digital twins

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27 Cybersecurity and privacy

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC38 Cloud

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 AI

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC32 Data management and interchange

Role

Convenor of ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41 AG25 and ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41 AG31. Expert member in the other groups.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supports my work in three different areas related to standardisation of data spaces, including architecture, interoperability and transversal aspects.

Regarding my contribution on data space architecture, this activity focus on bridging the gap lack of data space reference architecture, and lack of integration of the computing continuum

Defining the data space architecture is crucial since it is a prerequisite for the advent of the data economy, and the integration of IoT. The challenges of this effort concerns the complexity of data spaces ecosystem, complexity of agreeing on architecture standards, and integration of continuum

With regards to my contribution on data space semantic interoperability, there is a lack of guidance on interoperability and an urgent need to ensure the progress in interoperability. To achieve this, we need to agree on a method of semantic interoperability which reflects the past and the intended practice.

Finally, my contribution on transversal aspects of data spaces focus on developing guidance on the integration of security and privacy. Currently, this guidance is lacking, which is a barrier for compliance with regulation (e.g. CRA, AI act)

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

On data space architecture, I contribute to the following activities:

- ▶ Contribution on data space (ISO/IEC 20151) as liaison officer between SC41 to SC38.
- ▶ Submission of NP ISO/IEC 30152 Guidance on the connection of IoT and digital twins in data spaces (in SC41), as main editor. This involved the submission of an AIOTI report in May

2024, the official version of which will be published in September 2024.

- ▷ Submission of a NP ISO/IEC 30151 Digital Twin – Extraction and transactions of data products (in SC41), as co-editor.
- ▷ Co-edition of ISO/IEC 30188 Digital twin reference architecture (in SC41).
- ▷ Submission of an AIOTI report on the continuum based on the work carried out in the TF3 (architecture) of EUCloudEdgeIoT and applying for the creation of a PWI Architecture considerations for the IoT, Edge, Cloud, as editor with Lara Lopez (Eviden) as co-editor.

On data space interoperability, I work on:

- ▷ Liaising with SC32 from SC41 to ensure consistency between SC41 and SC32 standards on interoperability.
- ▷ Preparing the 2nd Working draft of ISO/IEC 21823-5 (behavioural and IoT interoperability) as editor, including a section in the annex to cover specific aspects of data spaces, e.g. data provenance. One option is to transfer this text to ISO/IEC 21823-1.
- ▷ Checking the relationship with IEC 63417 (Guide and plan to develop Smart energy Ontologies).
- ▷ Following the meetings on ISO/IEC 20151 (Dataspace concepts) in SC38 to ensure alignment with IoT standards.

On transversal aspects in data space, I manage:

- ▷ The preparation of the 2nd working draft of ISO/IEC 27115 (Cybersecurity assurance of complex systems) as co-editor.
- ▷ Follow up of ISO/IEC 27091 (AI privacy) as co-editor, but the progress is slow.
- ▷ The submission of NP ISO/IEC 27564 (guidance on the use of models in privacy engineering) as co-editor.
- ▷ The publication of ISO/IEC 30149 (IoT trustworthiness principles) as editor.
- ▷ Follow up of PWI 27568 (security and privacy of digital twins as editor. Progress is slowed down to ensure alignment with SC41 work on digital twins reference architecture.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The proposed standards on architecture and interoperability will enable SMEs to provide technology solutions. Standards will provide a stable business environment where SMEs can provide specific building blocks and know-how.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to several standardisation projects, including:

On data space architecture

- ▷ Contribution ISO/IEC 20151 Data space concepts
- ▷ Edition ISO/IEC 30152 Integration of IoT and digital twins in data spaces
- ▷ Co-edition ISO/IEC 30151 Digital Twin – Extraction and transactions of data products
- ▷ Co-edition ISO/IEC 30188 Digital Twin – Reference architecture
- ▷ Edition PWI Architecture considerations on IoT, Edge, Cloud

On data space interoperability

- ▷ Edition ISO/IEC 21823-5 IoT behavioural and policy interoperability
- ▷ Contribution IEC 63417 Guide and plan to develop Smart energy Ontologies

On transversal aspects in data space

- ▷ Co-edition ISO/IEC 27115 Cybersecurity assurance of complex system
- ▷ Edition PWI ISO/IEC 27116 Customised or multipurpose evaluation

- ▶ Co-edition ISO/IEC 27564 Guidance on the use of models in privacy engineering
- ▶ Edition ISO/IEC 27568 Security and privacy of IoT and digital twins

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute actively in writing different standardisation documents related to projects mentioned above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I continue working on these standardisation projects, including participating in different work meetings, editing the project documents and progressing on the working drafts.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/45086.html

 www.iso.org/committee/6483279.html

 www.iso.org/committee/45306.html

 www.iso.org/committee/601355.html

Role-based access control for electric power systems

Erik Andersen

*Contributor and co-editor, Andersen's L-Service
Denmark*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEC TC 57 WG 15 Power systems management and associated information exchange - Data and communication security

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

IEC 62351-8 is part of a series of smart grid standards aimed at protecting SCADA systems used in the electric grid. The SCADA protocols provide detailed specifications for controlling an electric power system. However, only authorised personnel should be allowed to do certain operations. A detailed and robust access control is required. The aim is to provide all the functions without overengineering the solution.

Every aspect of cybersecurity has a high priority. Access control needs to be timely in place to prevent unauthorised access. It is also a high priority to ensure that the proposed standard is complete in the sense that there is no way to shortcut security features.

It is quite a detailed and complex specification, so it is somewhat of a challenge to ensure consistency.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The fellowship has been important for making it possible to contribute to the quality of the draft standard. The proposed standard has been out for Committee Draft (CD) comment period. I have produced 52 comments which were submitted through the Danish Standard to the Committee Draft (CD). One of objectives was to simplify where required to achieve "security by simplicity". There has been one online resolution meeting where also the Danish comments were discussed. New resolution meetings are planned.

The standard in question is IEC 62351-8, Role-based access control for power system management.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society) Impact on Society

The IEC TC 57 WG 15 is an international standardisation organisation with participation from all parts of the world. It is useful that Europe is involved in this type of cybersecurity, which may affect future EU directives.

IEC 62351-8 is part of a series of smart grid standards aimed at protecting SCADA systems used in the electric grid. IEC 62351-8 together with other IEC 62351 standards, e.g., IEC 62351-4 or IEC 62351-5, provides a total cybersecurity solution for a specific area.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am an Editor for new and revised standards and an expert contributor to new and revised standards in the IEC 62351-x series.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have contributed to a technical report, IEC TR 63251-8.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The current status of the proposed standard is that it is in the Committee Draft state. If the comments resolution runs smoothly, the next state Draft International Standard (DIS) also called Inquiry stage.

The current state of my contribution is that the Danish ballot comments are defended as part of the resolution process and develop input to the DIS stage.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103;14:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2395,25

IEC 62351-90-4, Migration of cryptographic algorithms

Erik Andersen

*Contributor and co-editor, Andersen's L-Service
Denmark*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEC TC 57 WG 15, Electrical Electrotechnical Commission - Power systems management and associated information exchange - Data and communication security

Role

Project editor

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

It is recognized that currently used cryptographic algorithms and especially asymmetric algorithms will be broken by quantum computers. Different organisations like ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 2, NIST and IETF are successfully developing quantum-resistant cryptographic algorithms. However, experts working on quantum-resistant cryptography are skilled mathematicians and not protocol designers. It is necessary to close the gap between quantum-resistant cryptography development and communications protocols.

The purpose of the fellowship has been to develop procedures for how to migrate protocols to use the new types of cryptographic algorithms developed. The project suggests how to structure communications protocols in a way to facilitate migration and it proposes migration tools.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In addition to discussing migration techniques, the fellowship has contributed to recommendations for how to establish secure communications protocols. It is important that communication protocols utilise the full set of cryptographic algorithms (encryption digital signatures, key establishment, and integrity protection) and that certificates are used in a proper way. The standards in question for this fellowship is IEC 62351-90-4, Migration of cryptographic algorithms.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society) Impact on Society

When completed the first follow-up activity will start updating IEC 62351-4 to include cryptographic migration capabilities among other enhancements to prove its viability. It is expected to inspire others to consider this crucial issue and contribute with additional ideas. It is also expected that the specification will put light on the urgency of the subject.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, the new standard will be IEC 62351-90-4, Migration of Cryptographic algorithms.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have contributed to drafting the technical report on IEC 62351-90-4.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The draft IEC 62351-90-4 is in Committee Draft (CD) state and has gone through a comment period. These comments need resolution and a new document produced to be issued a Draft Technical Report to be submitted for vote and comments. After that, the document will be published as a Technical Report.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://1drv.ms/p/s!AtmOC_KXhCsTg7QIb1IDVaPbp2LfvQ?e=yRkR59

Developing cybersecurity standardisation for Artificial Intelligence and Internet of Things

François Lorek
Associate Director, TRAX
France

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 AHG3 AI & BD related Cybersecurity & Privacy coordination
ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG4 Security Controls & Services
ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 AHG2 IoT & Digital Twin related Cybersecurity & Privacy projects
Liaison representative/officer from ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 to ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42

Role

Convenor of ISO/IEC SC27 Adhoc Group 3 “Artificial Intelligence & Big Data”
Convenor support of ISO/IEC SC27 Adhoc Group 2 “Internet of Things & Digital Twins”
Convenor support of ISO/IEC WG4 “Security Controls & Services”
Editor of ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 Standing Document #27 Meeting Benefits and Requirements
Expert involved CEN/CENELEC JTC21

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Coordination and synchronisation between technical committees and working groups is one of the biggest challenges to face with lots of meetings on various interdependent topics (cybersecurity & privacy, artificial intelligence, ...) with several initiatives with different schedules at international, European and national scales. Priorities are given mostly by the European Commission, SDO's directives, market's expectations and the maturity of consensus between experts. Hopefully, lots of experts (especially European) are taking part to several cross work across TC's, SC's and WG's especially between AI (CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 & ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42) & Cybersecurity & Privacy (CEN/CENELEC JTC13 & ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27). At SC27 level, it is the reason for the establishment of Adhoc Group3 to ensure coordination on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big Data (BD) related security and privacy projects. Priorities are given by AI Act and associated standardisation requests while synchronising standardisation work within cybersecurity and privacy, especially when applied or touching AI, in a context with permanently evolving emerging technologies. The biggest challenge is ensuring consistent complementarity between Cybersecurity and Privacy standardisation work and AI standardisation activities supporting European AI regulations.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship allows me to take part to all meetings concerning Cybersecurity, Privacy and Artificial Intelligence (even most are very early or very late in the day, as per rules for scheduling in SDO's), whilst being able to keep delivering standard based consulting especially for SMEs which need to comply for ISO 27001 certifications mostly. This fellowship also allows me to join some important workshops which sometimes last a full day.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Many small and medium companies are about to be impacted by Cybersecurity & Privacy, IoT & DT or Artificial Intelligence standards or are concerned by Cybersecurity & Privacy within Artificial Intelligence with a need to make their market and potential customers confident, especially in the context of forthcoming standards related to regulations at European level (AI Act, ...) as well as European standardisation requests to be received by SDO's.

Impact on Society

Among others ISO officer duties and ISO/CEN/CENELEC standardisation expert I expect to provide the following benefits :

- ▷ Clarity of roadmap and scopes,
- ▷ Encourage constructive collaboration and participation of SC41 & SC42 experts in SC27 AhG2 & 3,
- ▷ Maintain a smooth and efficient organisation of working sessions,
- ▷ Full respect of directives and codes of ethics/conducts,
- ▷ Avoidance of starting un mature projects,
- ▷ Avoidance of misunderstandings between areas of work/officers/experts, potentially leading to inconsistent standards
- ▷ Monitoring the fair considerations of inputs from international experts (especially European ones no very experienced),

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute actively to the development of several new standards. Among others :

- ▷ ISO/IEC 27050-2:2018 IT - Electronic discovery — Part 2: Guidance for governance and management of electronic discovery
- ▷ ISO/IEC 27043:2015 IT - Security techniques — Incident investigation principles and processes
- ▷ ISO/IEC 27042:2015 IT - Security techniques — Guidelines for the analysis and interpretation of digital evidence
- ▷ ISO/IEC 27041:2015 IT - Security techniques — Guidance on assuring suitability and adequacy of incident investigative method
- ▷ ISO/IEC 27040:2015 IT - Security techniques — Storage security
- ▷ ISO/IEC 27039:2015 IT - Security techniques — Selection, deployment and operations of intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDPS)
- ▷ ISO/IEC 27038:2014 IT - Security techniques — Specification for digital redaction
- ▷ ISO/IEC 27037:2012 IT - Security techniques — Guidelines for identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute regularly to managing New Work Items and other standardisation project documents.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG4 is currently managing a portfolio of 100 standards. Being officer is a neverending duty, to organise and manage all the meetings related to new preliminary work items, new projects at various stages till publication, systematic revision of already published standards.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/45306.html>

Towards Standardized End-to-End Security for the Internet of Constrained Things

Johann Großschädl

*Software developer, University of Luxembourg
Luxembourg*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IETF Working Group on Lightweight Authentication and Key Exchange (LAKE)

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

For many IoT applications, the protocols for End-to-End (E2E) are key enablers to secure communication between IoT devices over an insecure network, e.g., DTLS 1.3 (RFC 9147) or EDHOC (RFC 9528). Optimized implementations of these protocols were shown to be capable to run on devices that are equipped with a 32-bit microcontroller (e.g., ARM Cortex-M4). However, there exist other classes of IoT devices that are severely more constrained in terms of computational resources, e.g., miniature sensors and actuators, which usually come with an 8 or 16-bit microcontroller and have just a few kB of RAM and a few dozen kB of flash memory. In order to not exhaust the scarce resources of such devices, a security protocol should ideally have a RAM footprint of about 1 kB and a code size of below 10 kB. Currently, no implementation of DTLS or EDHOC exists that would achieve these goals, and it is unclear whether E2E security under such constraints is feasible (and practical) at all.

The recently-introduced Disco protocol is a promising alternative to DTLS and EDHOC since it is a modern “clean-slate” approach to achieve E2E security with very low complexity and no legacy overheads. Disco consists of two sub-protocols, namely Noise for authentication and key establishment and Strobe, a permutation-based protocol for secure transfer of application data. Thanks to previous StandICT 2026.eu support (under open call 2), it was shown that an optimized implementation of Disco for 16-bit MSP430 microcontrollers, called IoTDisco, can achieve a RAM footprint of only 1.4 kB and a code size of 11.6 kB; both is very close to the mentioned goals. These results make Disco an interesting protocol for standardization. However, it is unclear how Disco and EDHOC compare when both are implemented for the same target device. The present project contributed to fill this gap by extending the IoTDisco prototype to run on 32-bit ARM Cortex-M3 microcontrollers.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Both DTLS 1.3 and EDHOC were developed by the IETF, the latter concretely by the Lightweight Authenticated Key Exchange (LAKE) Working Group (WG). As stated above, there exist software prototypes of EDHOC (developed by LAKE volunteers), which target devices equipped with 32-bit ARM Cortex-M4 microcontrollers. These prototypes contain optimized implementations of the underlying elliptic-curve cryptosystems for this specific architecture. On the other hand, the prototype of Disco (i.e., IoTDisco) and its cryptosystems

were optimized for a 16-bit MSP430 microcontroller to be able to assess its execution time, RAM footprint and code size on such a constrained platform. However, the computational capabilities of Cortex-M4 and MSP430 microcontrollers differ significantly (e.g., the M4 is able to execute a 32x32-bit multiplication in a single clock cycle, whereas the MSP430 can only perform 16x16-bit multiplications), which makes it difficult to analyze and compare the efficiency of the two protocols.

In order to enable a direct comparison of the execution time, RAM footprint, and code size of EDHOC and Disco, it is necessary to implement and evaluate them on a microcontroller platform that represents a middle ground between Cortex-M4 and MSP430, such as the ARM Cortex-M3. A Cortex-M3 microcontroller needs 3-5 clock for a 32x32-bit multiplication, which means its (cryptographic) performance is below that of the Cortex-M4, but exceeds that of the MSP430. The main outcome of this StandICT-funded project is an extension of the IoTDisco prototype to support 32-bit ARM Cortex-M3 microcontrollers, which includes highly-optimized Assembly implementations of the performance-critical cryptographic operations. A Cortex-M3 implementation of EDHOC will be provided by other LAKE volunteers. These implementations will shed new light on the individual strengths and weaknesses of EDHOC and Disco, and help pave the way to more efficient and lightweight E2E security protocols for the IoT.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Even though the Disco protocol is not yet used in real-world products, the underlying cryptographic primitives, e.g., X25519, are standardized and widely deployed. Therefore, the Assembly optimizations for Cortex-M3 developed in the course of this fellowship can be useful for European companies in the IoT space, including SMEs. ARM is a European company and the 32-bit ARM architecture was initially developed in Cambridge (U.K.). Major providers of tool-chains for ARM microcontrollers, such as Keil, have their headquarter in Europe. ARM Cortex-M3 microcontrollers are deployed in thousands of IoT devices of European companies in all segments of the Embedded/IoT industry, ranging from automotive appliances over industrial control systems to medical devices. Many of the companies that designed and/or manufactured these devices are SMEs; they will benefit from this project and the developed source code, which is freely available under an open-source license.

Impact on Society

The poor state of security in the IoT is a massive problem that constantly plagues individual users as well as organizations and enterprises. This project has contributed to improve the security of the IoT since cryptographically-strong E2E protocols are the foundation upon which secure architectures, systems and protocols can be built. E2E protocols are of course only one of many aspects that determine the real-world security of an application or system, but it is an essential one since without E2E protocols it would be next to impossible to ensure secure communication. However, to be suitable for deployment in IoT devices, an E2E protocol does not only need to be secure, but it must also be efficient. Efficiency is particularly important for resource-constrained embedded/IoT devices (e.g., RFID tags, sensor nodes, or smart cards) that are extremely limited in terms of computational power, memory, and energy supply. The poor state of security in the IoT world is not only caused by ignorance and bad development practices, but also (in part) by the fact that cryptographic algorithms and protocols can have a significant negative impact on the execution time, RAM footprint, and energy consumption of an application running in an IoT device. Therefore, it is crucial that E2E protocols considered for standardization are carefully evaluated to have detailed information about their efficiency on many different platforms. This project has contributed to a better understanding of the performance of Disco protocol on 32-bit ARM Cortex-M3 microcontrollers and how the Disco protocol compare with other E2E protocols, in particular EDHOC.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, this fellowship enables me to contribute to the development of a new standard. The proposal to standardize the Disco protocol (or a variant of the Disco protocol) will be further discussed at the LAKE WG meeting at IETF-121.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to drafting technical reports. In addition,

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

As a part of this fellowship I worked on a research paper describing (i) implementation details of the IoTDisco prototype (and its underlying cryptosystems), (ii) an analysis of execution time, RAM footprint and code size of IoTDisco on a cortex-M3 microcontroller , and (iii) a comparison with implementation results for the EDHOC protocol. This paper will be made available after the IETF-121 meeting in November 2024.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://github.com/JohGroLux/IoTDisco/>

 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/wg/lake/about/>

■ Developing ISO/IEC 29128 parts 2 and 3

Daniel Waszkiewicz

*Cryptography specialist, National Institute of Telecommunications
Poland*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1 SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection
WG 3 Security evaluation, testing and specification

Role

Co-editor

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

In this fellowship, I am addressing several critical gaps, priorities, and challenges in the European cybersecurity landscape. Specifically, I am focusing on the need for standardised verification methodologies for cryptographic protocols. My work aims to develop robust frameworks for the verification of cryptographic protocols within the security of ICT products, services, and processes, thereby enhancing resilience against cyber threats.

One of the key gaps I am addressing is the need for formal verification of cryptographic protocols. Formal verification has already been successfully implemented in the development of protocols like TLS 1.3 and MLS. However, there is currently no document that facilitates the standardisation of this process. The ISO/IEC 29128-2 standard is intended to fill this gap by providing a structured approach to the formal verification of cryptographic protocol specifications.

Additionally, beyond the verification of protocol specifications, there is a critical challenge in analysing the implementation of these protocols, particularly in addressing vulnerabilities related to programming errors. Incidents such as Heartbleed and attacks like Sweet32 have highlighted the risks associated with flaws in protocol implementation, even when the cryptographic algorithms themselves are sound. This is where the ISO/IEC 29128-3 standard comes into play, offering a solution to evaluate and mitigate threats arising from implementation flaws in cryptographic protocols.

Furthermore, this fellowship aligns with the objectives of the Cybersecurity Act (CSA) by contributing to the evolution of certification schemes, such as the forthcoming European Cybersecurity Certification scheme. Through these efforts, I am contributing to the creation of a more secure and resilient digital ecosystem across Europe.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship significantly contributes to the ICT Standards landscape by addressing the need for updated cryptographic protocol verification standards, particularly in alignment with the Cybersecurity Act (CSA). The European Cybersecurity Certification (EUCC) scheme has already recognized the outdated ISO/IEC 29128:2011 standard, which has been withdrawn. This highlights the urgent need to develop the new ISO/IEC 29128-2 and ISO/IEC 29128-3 standards. ISO/IEC 29128-2 will provide a structured approach for the formal verification of

cryptographic protocol specifications, while ISO/IEC 29128-3 will address the critical need for verifying protocol implementations. These efforts are essential for supporting the CSA's goal of a secure and resilient digital ecosystem across Europe.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

A unified approach to the verification of cryptographic protocols within cybersecurity certification schemes could significantly reduce the costs and workload associated with certifying composite products or services. By ensuring that protocols are rigorously verified according to standardised methodologies, the overall efficiency of the certification process would improve. This could, at least partly, lower the financial barriers for SMEs to enter the certification market, as the consistent and reliable verification of protocols would streamline the certification of more complex systems.

Impact on Society

The Cybersecurity Act (CSA) facilitates the use of certification as a powerful cybersecurity measure that can be implemented without additional burdens among Member States. In the past, products or services that were certified in one country often had to undergo similar certification procedures again if specific requirements were imposed by another country. However, with the introduction of the European Cybersecurity Certification (EUCC) scheme, all certificates issued under this scheme will be legally recognized across all Member States once the relevant Implementing Act comes into effect. This harmonisation is crucial in reducing duplication of efforts, saving time and costs, and ensuring consistent cybersecurity standards across Europe.

My primary focus is on developing standardised verification methodologies for cryptographic protocols, which are crucial for enhancing cybersecurity practices across Europe. My work is centred on creating robust frameworks for verifying cryptographic protocols within ICT products, services, and processes, ultimately strengthening resilience against cyber threats.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, this project is directly involved in the development of a new version of the outdated standard ISO 29128:2011. The updated ISO 29128 standard will now be divided into three parts, with the first part already developed and published as ISO/IEC 29128-1:2023. My work is focused on contributing to the remaining parts, ISO/IEC 29128-2 and ISO/IEC 29128-3, which are currently in the drafting phase. These new sections will enhance and expand the original standard, addressing both the formal verification of cryptographic protocols and the verification of their implementations.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have contributed to a technical report on development of the updated ISO 29128 standard.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Both considered standards, ISO 29128-2 and ISO 29128-3, are currently in the 2nd draft phase. According to the ISO schedule, the next step involves gathering comments and feedback on these drafts to inform the development of the 3rd working drafts. This phase is crucial as it allows for the refinement and enhancement of the standards based on expert input, ensuring they meet the necessary requirements for the verification of cryptographic protocols. The subsequent action will involve the integration of these comments and the finalisation of the 3rd drafts, which will bring us closer to the successful completion and adoption of these

standards. Following this, the focus will shift to the approval and publication process, ultimately providing a standardised framework for the formal verification and implementation analysis of cryptographic protocols, thereby strengthening cybersecurity practices globally.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/45306.html>

Advance Biometric System-On-Card (ISO/IEC 17839) Standard improvement

Pavel Cuchriajev

*Technical expert contributor; Standard Norge
Lithuania*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC SC17 WG11 Application of biometrics to cards and personal identification

Role

Expert

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The fellowship addresses gaps, priorities, and challenges in ICT standardisation through several key actions:

- ▶ **Advancing BSoC Standards:** Enhancing ISO/IEC 17839 series, particularly ISO/IEC 17839-1, -2, and -3, to ensure relevance in evolving BSoC technology.
- ▶ **Interoperability and Compliance:** Promoting consistent practices and compliance across sectors, fostering interoperability, especially among SMEs.
- ▶ **Privacy Preservation:** Safeguarding citizens' privacy, particularly in Europe, by storing biometric data exclusively on secure personal devices.
- ▶ **Industry Engagement:** Encouraging industry collaboration in the standardisation process, addressing declining expert participation.
- ▶ **Technology Advancements:** Incorporating recent technological developments and usability insights into BSoC standards to maintain relevance.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I significantly contributed to the ICT standards landscape by advancing the Biometric System-on-Card (BSoC) standards, particularly within the ISO/IEC 17839 series. By enhancing these standards, the application ensures BSoC technology aligns with industry best practices, promotes interoperability, and addresses emerging challenges. The application's involvement in ISO/IEC SC17 WG11 facilitates collaboration among industry stakeholders, promoting the adoption of standardised BSoC solutions. Specific ICT standards addressed include ISO/IEC 17839 series, ISO/IEC 24787, and ISO/IEC 7816-11. These standards define essential requirements for BSoC technology, ensuring secure identification and transaction authorization while preserving privacy. By contributing to the development of these standards, the funded application plays a pivotal role in shaping the ICT standards landscape, promoting innovation, security, and interoperability in BSoC technology.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

My contribution impacts European SMEs by providing clear guidelines for implementing Biometric System-on-Card (BSoC) technology. Standards promote interoperability, reduce costs, enhance trust, and foster innovation, enabling SMEs to compete effectively, access markets, and build credibility.

Impact on Society

The work supported societal impacts by enhancing security and privacy, facilitating access to services, supporting digital transformation, promoting innovation and economic growth, and protecting individual rights in the digital age.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I actively contributed to the development of ISO/IEC 17839 series: -1, -2 and -3.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

No.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

While work on ISO/IEC 17839-2 project is completed, there is still more work to be done on maturing ISO/IEC 17839-1/17839-3 before they can be promoted to next stages. Discussions will be continued in next working group meetings.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/45144.html

2. Key Enablers

Participation in standards development for Online Age Assurance ISO/IEEE/BSI/CEN-CENELEC

Iain Corby
Director, SafetyTech Limited
United Kingdom

Sector

Electronic Identification and Trust Services Including e-Signature

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17 Cards and security devices for personal identification
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17 WG10 Motor vehicle driver licence and related documents
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17 WG11 Application of biometrics to cards and personal identification
ISO/IEC JTC1 /SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection WG5 Identity management and privacy technologies
IEEE Working Group P2089.1

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

In the framework of this fellowship, I contribute to several different standardisation activities, including: a

- ▶ Addressing minor edits to IEEE 2089.1 and developing a Certification Scheme with IEEE
- ▶ Applying to IEEE CTSoc/ETSC to form a study group to develop a PAR on Parental Consent.
- ▶ Participation in BSI IST/33/5 and ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG5 re ISO 27566 Parts 1, 2 and 3
- ▶ ETSI STF 681 Age Verification Expert Member.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

I continue to drive forward the development of standards with multiple organisations.

Regarding IEEE 2089.1 With the standard now approved, we are setting up a certification scheme with a conformity assessment body (the Age Check Certification Scheme) and IEEE. Also, minor errata are being corrected through a new PAR.

Regarding, IEEE 2089.x Parental Consent. IEEE CTSoc/ETSC is now holding a meeting in October 2024 to determine if I can chair a new study group to develop a PAR for this.

Regarding CAN/DGSI 127: Age Verification Technologies - I am a member of the working group and provided extensive revisions to drafting for this standard currently out for Review by DGSI Technical Committee

In addition I follow several meetings of IST/33/5 to review the Committee Draft of ISO 27566-1 and dispose of comments on 27566-2 and drafting of 27566-3.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society) Impact on Society

Europe is legislating at pace to create legal demands for online age assurance (verification and estimation) but standards are falling behind. There is an urgent need which standards can be addressed in Europe. The ISO is working in parallel on 27566, to which I also contribute, but that is still at the working draft stage and is only a framework, not a best practice guide. Standards for AV and parental consent are also needed in North America, India, Australia, Indonesia, Oman and Canada, amongst others, due to new legislation.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am contributing to the development of several standards, including namely the updates of IEEE 2089.1 and drafting a new standard, IEEE 2089.x Parental Consent.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I am contributing to the development of several standards documents.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Aiming to complete a first draft of IEEE 2089.x Parental Consent within the current grant period, by the end of November 2024, subject to approval by IEEE CTSoc/ETSC

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/45144.html>

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/45306.html>

Develop Amendment to extensible minutiae standard ISO/IEC 39794-2

Robert Mueller

*Independent consultant, Dr. Robert Mueller IT Consulting
Germany*

Sector

Electronic Identification and Trust Services Including e-Signature

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC SC37 Biometrics WG3 Biometric data interchange formats

Role

Expert member and editor of ISO/IEC 39794-2.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The data format and compliance standards developed in ISO/IEC SC37 WG3 are used in Europe and world-wide for storing and transferring biometric data. Standardised formats enable interoperability across countries and industrial organisations. The currently published standards from ISO/IEC 19794 series have several flaws with respect to forward and backward compatibility as well as XML and ASN.1 compliance. SC37 therefore decided to develop the ISO/IEC 39794 series specifying extensible formats that are future proof.

Part 2 specifically covers finger minutiae as one of the most prominent biometric data formats.

The standard ISO/IEC 39794-2 has been brought to publication which was already sponsored by a previous StandICT.eu fellowship. It has been recognized during the FDIS stage that there is a defect in the standard affecting its backward compatibility. Technical comments were no longer possible according to ISO regulations. The working group SC37 decided that a technical corrigendum should be issued and I was nominated as the editor.

In this role, I collect comments from national bodies, prepare a proposed disposition and resulting new base text for advancing to ballot.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The standardisation landscape for biometrics is evolving due to increased interest in automated identification of citizens for civil and governmental applications.

This has strengthened further during the pandemic avoiding personal contact and automating processes such as border management within the EU. The data formats specified by WG3 are used in various application profiles including also civil applications like e.g. payment or physical access control.

Standardised data formats for biometric data like ISO/IEC 39794-2 are essential for widespread adoption and interoperability. They allow common interfaces and exchanging components for various levels of a technical solution to be exchanged.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Standardised biometric data formats enable interoperability and exchanging system components like biometric capture devices, algorithms, storage systems. This is of particular relevance for SMEs who typically provide only a single component rather than an entire solution like industry leading large corporations – which sometimes may rely on proprietary data formats.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am the editor of the technical corrigendum amendment to ISO/IEC 39794-2.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I manage the proposed disposition of comments during the cycle period PDAM ISO/IEC 39794-2.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

In the framework of this fellowship, I have drafted the amendment text and sent it as a first proposal for commenting. A letter ballot passed, and comments were received from national bodies. A proposed disposition of comments was created and submitted to the secretariat. These have been discussed in the working group meeting in Bertinoro, Italy in July 2024. The result is an approved disposition of comments and, in my role as the editor, I provided a revised base text for the amendment to be used in the next cycle. Therefore, the status of the work is in progress.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/313770.html>

Write a specification for a W3C VC Data Integrity suite that is compliant with JAdES

Markus Sabadello

CTO, Danube Tech GmbH
Austria

Sector

Electronic Identification and Trust Services Including e-Signature

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

W3C Credentials Community Group

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Verifiable Credentials (VCs, standardised at the W3C) are an important technical building block in many (decentralised) digital identity projects around the world, including the EU's Digital Wallet initiative following the approval of the eIDAS 2.0 regulation. VCs are secured by digital signatures that provide integrity and authenticity of the information in it. This seems simple, however, there is tremendous complexity in today's technical landscape due to a wide variety of (non-interoperable) technical choices in VC formats and securing mechanisms, as well as various hybrid formats.

An important term in the eIDAS 2.0 regulation is Qualified Electronic Attestations of Attributes (QEAs), which are essentially the same concept as Verifiable Credentials, but will be legally recognized in the EU, due to the use of Trust Service Providers (TSPs) and a specific signature format (JAdES). At the moment however, there is no defined way how JAdES signatures can be applied to Verifiable Credentials.

The "gap" therefore exists between the two important technologies mentioned above, i.e. the W3C Verifiable Credential Data Model 2.0 and JAdES (ETSI TS 119 182-1), which together will constitute an optimal technical basis for the EU Digital Wallet under the eIDAS 2.0 regulation.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The standards I am dealing with are the W3C Verifiable Credential Data Model (VCDM) 2.0 in conjunction with the W3C Verifiable Credential Data Integrity 1.0 specification for securing VCs. The contribution of this project will be a specification for a new W3C VC Data Integrity suite, i.e. a mechanism for securing Verifiable Credentials (VCs). Data Integrity suites provide a pluggable extensibility point for securing Verifiable Credentials in different ways. Verifiable Credentials are already widely used by various European initiatives and infrastructures, such as the European Blockchain Service Infrastructure (EBSI), Gaia-X, and others. They have also been used heavily in various NGI funding programs, such as NGI Essif-Lab.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society) Impact on Society and SMEs

In the coming years, the eIDAS 2.0 regulation and associated EU Digital Identity Wallet will become available to all EU citizens and are expected to have a major impact on various parts of our (digital) societies. There will also be various opportunities for SMEs to participate in a European digital identity ecosystem, for example by providing software and consulting services.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

The final deliverable of this fellowship will not be a final standard, but a specification for a new W3C VC Data Integrity suite, i.e. a mechanism for securing Verifiable Credentials (VCs), using the JAdES signature format. It will be hosted as a work item at the W3C Credentials Community Group (CCG). At a later point in time, the specification could potentially undergo a formal standardisation process.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to technical specifications for a new W3C VC Data Integrity suite.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The first step of my fellowship focused on researching and planning how the relevant technologies fit together, i.e. W3C Verifiable Credential Data Model 2.0 and JAdES (ETSI TS 119 182-1). I have also researched and commented on related efforts such as SD-JWT VC, and SD-JWT VC DM, which have similar goals. I have started to work on the actual specification that is the subject of this project, and this will be published as a second step of the fellowship.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.w3.org/community/credentials/>

Guidelines for the Data Management within On-Boarded European Digital Identity Wallets

Raul Sanchez-Reillo

*Full professor and the University Group for Identification Technologie, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Spain*

Sector

Electronic Identification and Trust Services, Including e-Signature

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/TC 224 Personal identification and related personal devices with secure elements, systems, operations and privacy in a multi-sectoral environment WG 20 Ad Hoc Group on European Digital Identity Wallets

Role

PWI Proposer, Editor, Contributor and Co-convenor

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

CEN TC224 WG20 is a Working Group created to standardise all aspects related to the specification of the European Digital Identity Wallet (EUDIW). WG20 started with the analysis of the gaps in the standardisation world, when trying to apply current technology to the concept of a future EUDIW. This gap analysis was published under the Technical Report CEN/TR 17982:2023 "European Digital Identity Wallets standards Gap Analysis".

While developing such a technical report, it was detected that an initial work needed is to define the guidelines for the on-boarding of the identity data into the wallet. That started the drafting of prCEN/TS 18098 "Guidelines for the onboarding of user personal identification data within European Digital Identity Wallets" which is currently in development.

But this technical specification only takes care of the on-boarding process, not the handling of information in the EUDIW after the PID has been on-boarded.

Hence, my fellowship is focused on launching a new Preliminary Work Item (PWI), to define the guidelines for the data management within the EUDIW, once it has already passed the on-boarding process. This means covering the aspects such as:

- ▶ Updating details within the Personal Identity Data (PID)
- ▶ Adding credentials / attributes / attestations related to that PID
- ▶ Renewing the validity of the information inside the EUDIW

This has not been covered in previous works, so this significant gap is the one to be closed by this NWI. Therefore the challenge is to get a convincing proposal to be approved for start working in the edition of this NWI at CEN TC224 WG20. Once approved, the second main challenge is to provide a first draft of the text, to start the commenting cycles. The third challenge, from the editorial point of view, is to develop this draft using the new OSD platform available in CEN (and also in ISO).

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

When a sudden interest is created, there is a risk that both technological and standardisation works will be developed in different lines, contradicting one to each other. Therefore, it is a must to coordinate all those efforts, trying to reach a common ground and reduce the workload and the risk of creating a non-usable product.

The NWI proposed in this fellowship will take as the normative references the following documents:

- ▷ CEN/TR 17982:2023 “European Digital Identity Wallets standards Gap Analysis”
- ▷ prCEN/TS 18098 “Guidelines for the onboarding of user personal identification data within European Digital Identity Wallets”
- ▷ ISO/IEC JTC1/SC17 AG3 Annual Reports
- ▷ ISO/IEC 18013-5 “Personal identification — ISO-compliant driving licence — Part 5: Mobile driving licence (mDL) application”
- ▷ ISO/IEC TS 18013-7 “Personal identification — ISO-compliant driving licence — Part 7: Mobile driving licence (mDL) add-on functions”
- ▷ ISO/IEC 23220 series “Cards and security devices for personal identification — Building blocks for identity management via mobile devices”
- ▷ And all documents generated by the European Commission about the eIDAS2 regulation, including the ARF and the forthcoming Implementing Acts.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

When the European Identity Wallet will be defined, all service providers will have to adapt their services to use that wallet. Most of services providers are either SMEs or use solutions developed by SMEs, so the definition of that identity wallet will have a major impact on the activities of those SMEs, increasing their workload, and therefore, their benefits

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

The target of my fellowship is to be able to approve and start the development of a Preliminary Work Item titled “Guidelines for the Data Management within On-Boarded European Digital Identity Wallets” in CEN TC224 WG20.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to the technical specifications, in a Preliminary Work Item titled “Guidelines for the Data Management within On-Boarded European Digital Identity Wallets”.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

There have been negotiations to agree on a PWI Proposal form to be launched, both within the Spanish NB, and within CEN TC224 WG20 experts. These negotiations have taken more time than initially expected but are being sent to CEN TC224 Secretary by the end of July 2024, to start the NP ballot before the summer ends. In order to recover the current delay, the edition of the first WD will start immediately, in anticipation of a positive result of the NP ballot

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:6205&cs=1E59B4D3EFD280E27AAC0C16CC13CD4FD

Convenorship for AI Act Standardization Request CEN CENELEC JTC 21 WG Cybersecurity

Annegrit Seyerlein-Klug

*Standardisation manager for neurocat GmbH,
Germany*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN CENELEC JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence WG5 Joint working for Cybersecurity for AI- systems
CEN CENELEC JTC 21 WG2 risk-management; conformity assessment
CEN CENELEC JTC 21 WG4 trustworthiness framework
CEN/CENELEC JTC 13 WG9 CRA SR currently in discussions
ISO IEC SC 42 AHG Liaison to SC 27 for Cybersecurity
ISO IEC SC 27 WG 4 ISO/IEC 27090 Cybersecurity — Artificial Intelligence — Guidance for addressing security threats to artificial intelligence systems

Role

Convenor of CEN CENELEC JTC 21 WG5 Joint working for Cybersecurity for AI- systems and expert in the other groups.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

I focus on AI and Cybersecurity, which has unfortunately very few experts. Most of the engaged experts are only working in Cybersecurity or AI and understanding of each other is difficult. There is a gap of knowledge about Cybersecurity and AI, but also in the knowledge within participating organisations, who lack training and expertise of the existing regulation and standards in Cybersecurity and AI as well as the concept of cybersecurity and of standardisation itself. Furthermore, very often, cybersecurity experts lack knowledge in AI.

The standardisation request for AI-Systems as a product, in my case for cybersecurity as a horizontal requirement, has not very many examples, so we work on a new area.

A lot of research work has to be done by my working group, CEN CENELEC JTC 21 WG5, and I, which is normally not a direct part of the standardisation. We are working in WG5 as much as possible to close the gaps.

Hence, my priority is the Convenorship of CEN CENELEC JTC21 WG 5, the organisation and project support to work on the AI Act standardisation request for Cybersecurity. This includes a lot of collaboration with other groups within JTC 21, JTC 13, ISO IEC SC 42 and SC 27 to collect all information of existing and work under development.

The main challenge is that JTC21 and also our WG5 has a diverse structure of experts and knowledge, which makes the work, the effort and efficiency very difficult. In our case, the challenge in addition is the collaboration with other existing standardisation groups within JTC 21 as well as with JTC 13 for Cyber Resilience Act, with ETSI and their view, with ISO IEC SC 27 and SC 42.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

I work as convenor and expert direct for the harmonised standards relating to the AI Act, especially for the SR#8 Cybersecurity. We are working on specific homegrown standards for Cybersecurity for AI-systems including Cybersecurity risk management. Also we support ISO/IEC SC 27 standard 27090 as guidance for our planned homegrown standard with requirements. I organise the interaction with JTC 13 for the interplay of the harmonised standards Cybersecurity for the AI Act as well as for harmonised standards for the Cyber Resilience Act. They need to be in alignment.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

My work in JTC 21 WG 5 shall be usable also for SME ´s and the European societies, because Cybersecurity is elementary for every digital asset and very important also for AI-Systems as a digital asset to be secure, safe, healthy and respecting fundamental rights.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am contributing activity for a new work item NWIP within CEN CENELEC JTC 21 WG5 "Artificial Intelligence - Cybersecurity specifications for AI systems" and we start developing the standard on the basis of the gap report.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to the development of a gap analysis report.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Now we that the NWIP has been approved, and our WG5 group starts developing the standard on the base of the gap report

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

The EU Path to AI: AI Trustworthiness, AI Ethics, Green & Sustainability AI, Fundamental Rights

Enrico Panai

AI and Data Ethicist, Sardus France France

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN CENELEC JTC21 AI WG4 Foundational and societal aspects
ISO/IEC JTC1 SC 42 AI WG3 Trustworthiness
AFNOR ethics committee on AI

Role

Convenor of CEN CENELEC JTC21 AI WG4 Foundational and societal aspects

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My work focus on the different aspects of artificial intelligence, including:

- ▶ “AI Trustworthiness Framework” The project aims to establish a harmonised standard to help businesses comply with the EU AI Act. Although it was initially conceived as an “entry point” standard to direct towards other standards, it is now attempting to fill the gap left by the absence of other regulatory documents. This project is of utmost priority as the deadlines are imposed by the European AI Act. The biggest challenge is achieving the necessary level of granularity required by the EC through consensus.
- ▶ Ethical Projects: The “Competence Requirements for AI Ethicists Professionals” project is currently in its final phase and should go under ballot by the end of the year. The “Guidelines AI Ethical Aspects Management in AI Systems Lifecycle” project has been joined by the “Guidance for upskilling organisations on AI ethics and social concerns” project, and its launch is expected at the next plenary in November. The “Impact Assessment in the Context of Fundamental Rights” project is currently developing a catalogue of use cases showing the impact of certain AI systems on Fundamental Rights. One of the main challenges for these projects is having a sufficient number of experts, as technical standardisation is mainly composed of technical figures.
- ▶ Sustainable AI Projects: The “Environmentally Sustainable Artificial Intelligence” project is in its final stages with Afnor. The “Sustainable Artificial Intelligence – Guidelines and Metrics for the Environmental Impact of Artificial Intelligence Systems and Services” project is in its early stages. The output is currently being defined.
- ▶ Other Projects in Parallel Development: The “Information Technology - Artificial Intelligence - Transparency Taxonomy of AI Systems” project is in its final phase with ISO guidance. The “AI-Enhanced Nudging” project (of which I am also editor) is requesting an 18-month extension on the timeline.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship supports my continuous engagement in the role of convenor of CEN/CENELEC JTC1 21 WG4 and my involvement in numerous ongoing standardisation projects in the field of ethical AI. This fellowship supports my investment across different standardisation projects on AI, including: .

- ▶ AI trustworthiness framework (JT021008)
- ▶ Environmentally sustainable Artificial Intelligence (JT021010)
- ▶ Competence requirements for AI ethicists professionals (JT021019)
- ▶ Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Transparency taxonomy of AI systems (ISO/IEC DIS 12792:2024) (JT021022)
- ▶ Guidance for upskilling organisations on AI ethics and social concerns (JT021033)
- ▶ Guidelines on tools for handling ethical issues in AI system life cycle (JT021034)
- ▶ Sustainable Artificial Intelligence – Guidelines and metrics for the environmental impact of artificial intelligence systems and services (JT021035)
- ▶ AI-Enhanced Nudging (ISO/IEC AWI 25029) (JT021003)

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

The development of the AI Trustworthiness Framework is highly significant as it directly supports the implementation of the EU AI Act. This framework establishes essential standards that will enable organisations to meet the legal requirements of the Act

The ethical standards initiatives are particularly important for SMEs, as they provide the necessary guidance to address the residual uncertainties surrounding AI implementation. By helping SMEs employ competent ethicists, choose the right tools, and upskill the ethical awareness of developers, these efforts ensure that smaller enterprises can foster responsible innovation.

The ongoing work on sustainable AI is preparing organizations for compliance with forthcoming EU regulations on environmental sustainability. These initiatives focus on creating AI systems that are energy-efficient and environmentally responsible, ensuring that businesses are not only able to meet the new regulatory standards.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, this fellowship supported me to work on several ongoing standardisation projects listed above.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute continuously to drafting European and international standards, technical reports and guidelines.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

As a convenor of a working group, given the enormous workload, the StandICT.eu funding helps to cover (even if only partially) the loss of professional activities. However, I believe that rather than increasing individual funding, it would be more beneficial for certain roles (such as chair and convenors) to have the option to nominate secretariat staff for funding to assist in the process. In fact, due to the workload and pressure, a significant amount of time is wasted on administrative tasks that could be delegated.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

 www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html

Building trustworthiness for artificial intelligence

Piercosma Bisconti Lucidi

*Researcher in AI Ethics, Co-Founder of DEXAI – Artificial Ethics, Italian Interuniversity Consortium for Computer Science
Italy*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN CENELEC JTC21 AI WG2 Operational aspects
CEN CENELEC JTC21 AI WG4 Foundational and societal aspects
ISO/IEC SC 42 JTC1 WG3 on “AI trustworthiness”

Role

CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 project leader and editor of “AI Trustworthiness Framework”

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

For what concerns gaps, I am addressing the standardisation of AI systems, with particular focus on addressing the standardisation request of the European Commission in relation with the AI Act. The grace period given to high-risk AI systems under the AI Act is 24 months, and CEN-CENELEC standardisation activities need to work at a fast pace to meet the deadline with standards ensuring AI Act practical implementation. This is an outstanding challenge I am currently addressing being the project leader of the overarching “AI Trustworthiness Framework”. The development of this standard represents a priority in the AI standardisation landscape in order to provide companies, organisations, and SMEs with an entry point to the standards for AI in the EU, and delivering the high-level requirements that will ensure the protection of fundamental rights. The second challenge is the gaps between standards under development inside the CEN-CENELEC, and the complexity of their interplay. This issue might constitute an outstanding barrier for CEN-CENELEC standards toward a full coverage of the EU AI Act. In fact, some provisions might remain unaddressed, ultimately delaying or hindering the full application of the AI Act in the EU environment. The “AI Trustworthiness Framework” aims to fill these gaps by putting forth those requirements that remained unaddressed in order to cover the AI Act provisions, and examine the interplay between the different requirements of other standards, to understand if there are overlaps or contradictions that need to be addressed. Moreover, AI ethics is a field that is still highly qualitative and poorly systematic. I am contributing in the standardisation activities of AI Ethics to provide the EU environment with clear methodologies to address ethical challenges of AI systems.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In my role as project leader and editor of the ‘AI Trustworthiness Framework’, I am guiding this crucial task group to establish an overarching standard. This standard is intended to serve as the industry entry point for the 10 items specified in the standardisation request. The concept of trustworthiness, central since the High-Level Expert Group on AI’s White Paper ‘Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI’, defines our approach. To ensure trustworthiness in Artificial

Intelligence means that AI systems are capable of 'meeting stakeholders' expectations in a verifiable way'. In the EU context, this entails that AI systems will respect and reflect EU values and fundamental rights. The objective of this task group is to support the AI standardisation request by providing guidance and requirements to stakeholders. This guidance will inform the use of standards identified in the Architecture of Standards. The project's aim is to develop a standard on the AI trustworthiness framework that ensures actionability for all stakeholders and sectors. Its goal is to bring consistency, comprehensiveness, and alignment to high-level horizontal requirements. To achieve this, the following objectives have been set:

1. To put forth high level horizontal requirements for AI systems.
2. We will work toward bringing consistency and harmonisation between the different standards developed under JTC21, to fill the current gaps in order to support the EU AI Act.
3. We will develop a contextualization methodology to contextualise high-level horizontal requirements to specific domains of applications or stakeholders. This methodology will be a guidance on how to tailor the horizontal requirements to specific domains of applications that might require additional measures to ensure trustworthiness.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Industries and SMEs in the EU are facilitated in adopting standards. One of the main barriers for standard adoption is the complexity of the standardisation processes. In order to claim conformity, multiple requirements coming from multiple standards should be met. The AI Trustworthiness Framework will serve as an entry point for industries and SMEs in order to facilitate this process, fostering conformity and facilitating industry competitiveness.

Impact on Society

One of the outstanding barriers in the deployment of innovative technologies is social acceptance. This barrier damages both the economic benefits and the social benefits of designing innovative AI systems. The AI Trustworthiness Framework will reinforce social trust in AI systems, by providing companies, consumers and ultimately citizens with a clear understanding of the fundamental requirements for trustworthy AI.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am contributing, as project leader, to a new standard within JTC21 WG4 AI Trustworthiness Framework.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, an EN supposed to be harmonised against articles 11-15 of the AI Act: the AI Trustworthiness Framework.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The standardisation project is progressing: We now have a first working draft, nearly read. We are going to ballot in mid October 2024, and hopefully to enquiry around the end of this year or the beginning of 2025.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:29:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D#1

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

Supporting the AI Act with standards for trustworthy systems and datasets in AI and NLP

Lauriane Aufrant

*NLP researcher in academia, Inria
France*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 Artificial intelligence WG 1 Foundational standards
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 WG 3 Trustworthiness
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 WG 5 Computational approaches and computational characteristics of Artificial Intelligence systems
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 JWG 2 Testing of AI-based systems
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 JWG 5 Natural language processing
CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 Artificial intelligence WG 1 Strategic Advisory Group
CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 WG 2 Operational aspects
CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 WG3 Engineering aspects
CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 WG4 Foundational and societal aspects
CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 WG 5 Cybersecurity aspects
AFNOR/CN IA Artificial intelligence

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My efforts are currently focused on answering the standardisation request that CEN-CENELEC JTC21 received from the European Commission in relation to the AI Act. As the target dates grow closer, it seems that the current pool of experts is not sufficient to answer the diverse needs expressed in the request. I have thus initiated reinforced outreach efforts, as well as onboarding sessions for new experts. It also appeared that there remains many gaps and inconsistencies in the existing landscape of AI standardisation projects in JTC 21 (& ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42), which started to hinder the correct development of requirements expected by the EC (e.g. standard on bias for classification/regression systems, but not other AI systems; evaluation metrics for classification and for NLP but not for clustering for instance): I have contributed to initiating new work on a number of those gaps. It was on my initiative that JTC 21 created a Technical Coherence Forum that is investigating exactly those questions. Overall, I am taking right now a more holistic view on the AI standardisation roadmap, while pursuing in parallel my contributions to specific AI standards in SC 42 and JTC 21.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Being an active member of many related working groups, I am in an ideal position to contribute to the technical alignment among those standards and refine their interplay.

I do so as a core member of the CEN-CENELEC JTC 21/WG 1/Technical Coherence Forum, but also in ISO/IEC AWI 24970 on AI logging or in JTC 21 on work item JT021024 on AI Risk Management for instance.

I am also using those insights to help the incubation of several new standardisation projects (computer vision tasks, computer vision evaluation, JT021029 cybersecurity of AI systems, JT021011 quality management system for regulatory purposes).

As for drafting activities, I am currently contributing substantial text and inputs to ISO/IEC 24029-3 (statistical assessment of robustness), ISO/IEC AWI 23282 (NLP evaluation), ISO/IEC 4213 (generic performance metrics), JT021036 "Concepts, measures and requirements for managing bias in AI systems" and JT021037 "Quality and governance of datasets in AI".

I also participate actively in other standards that are more in a consensus-building phase, where the concepts or general approach still need to be consolidated: ISO/IEC 22989 AMD 1 (terminology of generative AI), ISO/IEC WD 42102 (taxonomy of AI methods and capabilities), JT021008 (AI Trustworthiness Framework).

Finally, I am helping the finalisation of ISO/IEC TR 23281 (NLP tasks) and ISO/IEC DIS 12792 (AI transparency).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

There is growing concern regarding the impact of the upcoming AI Act on the activity of SMEs in that field. While it is feared that a large number of standards associated to the AI Act could create an excessive burden for SMEs to understand and implement the new requirements, on the other hand if there remain gaps in the standards' coverage of the AI landscape, this will create huge challenges for SMEs whose products sit precisely in such areas (inability to comply). I have started to make increased efforts to reach out to SMEs and collect their views and needs in those regards, and I am leveraging those inputs throughout my contributions in the various standards as well as in coordination.

In parallel, and beyond the considerations for the AI Act, I am also including in my work (in particular my NLP work) continuous considerations for interoperability aspects, which appear to be key to enable easier entry into the market for European SMEs.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, in the framework of this fellowship, I have played an active part in four new standardisation projects that are currently under ballot (computer vision tasks, computer vision evaluation, JT021029 cybersecurity of AI systems, JT021011 quality management system for regulatory purposes), as well as incubating the revision (with scope expansion) of ISO/IEC 4213 which has just been approved and is currently starting.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have actively contributed to the technical reports of the four standardisation projects named here above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The target date for the AI Act standardisation request is April 2025 for publication of the standards. This means that the core work of initial drafting would have to be completed already, in order to leave enough time for the multiple rounds of commenting and comment resolution. For various reasons including international dynamics, this is not the case to date, and some of the necessary standards are not even started. It is assumed that the EC will provide a 6-month extension given that the publication of the AI Act itself has been delayed,

but no further extension is expected. The pace of the work will thus have to be increased in order to meet the target dates, and innovative ways of working and of organising the deliverables are currently being discussed to enable that.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

Trustworthy AI and AI Risk Management expertise for EU AI Act harmonized standards

Anita Prinzie

VP Product, Omina Technologies

Belgium

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence WG 4 Foundational and societal aspects

CEN JTC 21 WG 2 AI Engineering

CEN JTC 21 TG 2 Risk Management

Role

Expert Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The AI Act is a European regulation promoting the uptake of human-centric and trustworthy AI, while ensuring protection of health, safety, and fundamental rights. Companies can prove conformity with the AI Act by complying with the 10 harmonised standards drafted by CEN-CENELEC. My fellowship contributes to two harmonised standards supporting the AI Act:

Firstly, I work on EN AI Trustworthiness Framework, which is a framework for AI systems' trustworthiness which contains terminology, concepts, high-level horizontal requirements, guidance and a method to contextualise those to specific stakeholders, domains or applications. The standard serves as an entry point to other harmonised standards providing detailed requirements on different aspects of AI system trustworthiness such as robustness, risk management, etc. The challenge is that trustworthiness requirements on the AI System level: ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 does not provide requirements. Also, ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 does not reflect the European values nor the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.

Secondly, I contribute to EN AI System Risk Management which offers horizontal requirements for a risk management system for AI Systems throughout their lifecycle to prevent or minimise health, safety or fundamental rights risks.

Currently there is a gap in the risk management of the AI system. ISO 31000:2018: risk management on the organisational level is not tailored to use of AI systems. ISO 23894:2023 risk management related to AI on the organisational level.

The aim is to ensure product safety including fundamental rights for a broad range of products and to extend ISO 14971:2019 to include other products than medical devices.

Also, the goal is to enable integrated risk management on the product and AI system level by providing methods to integrate risk management for an AI system which is a product safety component with the risk management for the overall product

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship contributes to a first draft of the prEN AI Trustworthiness Framework (WI=JT021008) and prEN AI System Risk Management (WI=JT021024) of CEN-CENELEC,

JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence, WG 4 and WG 2 respectively. As an expert in AI, AI Governance, product management and innovation management in various industries both for SMEs and enterprises, I draft, review, comment on the requirements to enable the design and management of trustworthy AI systems that proactively respect European norms and values and fundamental rights. Responsible yet affordable innovation with fast launch to market for all companies including SMEs: ensuring concrete requirements that can be integrated in existing trustworthy AI and risk management processes and day-to-day business operations.

The prEN AI Trustworthiness Framework uses definitions from EN ISO/IEC 22989:2023. Other standards provide more detailed requirements on different AI System trustworthiness aspects: robustness (prEN ISO/IEC 24029), accuracy (prEN ISO/IEC 23282, ISO/IEC TS 4213:202), data governance and quality for AI (FprCEN/CLC/TR 18115, ISO/IEC 5259 part 1-4), transparency and documentation (prEN ISO/IEC 12792), record keeping through logging (prEN ISO/IEC 24970), cybersecurity (prEN Cybersecurity specifications for AI Systems), AI systems risk management (prEN AI System Risk Management), and quality management (EN ISO/IEC 25059:2024). This standard also lays the groundwork for future vertical, product-specific AI Trustworthy standards.

The prEN AI System Risk Management complements ISO 31000:2018 and ISO 23894:2023 by providing risk management of the AI system. The prEN AI System Risk Management complements ISO 14971:2019 and ISO 12100:2010 by extending risk management to a broad range of products. This standard lays the groundwork for vertical/product/AI-technology-specific AI System Risk Management standards.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

I review and contribute to the prEN AI Trustworthiness Framework and prEN AI Risk Management accounting for the SME inclusiveness of the requirements. I want to enable SMEs to provide and/or deploy trustworthy AI systems while controlling AI risks taking into account their modest resources as compared to enterprises.

Impact on Society

The prEN AI Trustworthiness Framework Standard specifies trustworthiness requirements aligned with European culture and society. Whereas, the prEN AI System Risk Management standard enables to control risks not only on the individual and company level but also on the level of the society.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to drafting new standards. Firstly, The prEN AI Trustworthiness Framework uses definitions from EN ISO/IEC 22989:2023. Other standards provide more detailed requirements on different AI System trustworthiness aspects: robustness (prEN ISO/IEC 24029), accuracy (prEN ISO/IEC 23282, ISO/IEC TS 4213:202, NWIP Evaluation methods for accurate computer vision systems), data governance and quality for AI (FprCEN/CLC/TR 18115, ISO/IEC 5259 part 1-4), transparency and documentation (prEN ISO/IEC 12792), record keeping through logging (prEN ISO/IEC 24970), cybersecurity (prEN Cybersecurity specifications for AI Systems), AI systems risk management (prEN AI System Risk Management), and quality management (EN ISO/IEC 25059:2024).

Secondly, the prEN AI System Risk Management complements ISO 31000:2018 and ISO 23894:2023 by providing requirements for AI System risk management, extends ISO 14971:2019 and ISO 12100:2010 to a broad range of products. This standard lays the groundwork for future vertical/product/AI-technology-specific standards.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

My fellowship contributes to the two deliverables of a draft prEN AI Trustworthiness Framework and a second draft of prEN AI Risk Management.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The commenting process of the draft prEN AI Risk Management standard is now running, and I will add comments to the draft before its final submission. I am also processing final contributions to prEN AI Trustworthiness Framework. Once the drafts are finalised, they will be published for the next steps towards a definitive standard.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

 <https://www.standict.eu/discussion-groups/artificial-intelligence/267/managing-safety-health-and-fundamental-right-risks-ai>

Cybersecurity standards for AI systems in response to the EC standardisation request (AI Act)

Francisco Medeiros-Filho

*Independent expert, FM Tech Consult BV
Belgium*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 Cybersecurity for AI Systems
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG1 Strategic Advisory Group.

Role

Co-Convenor of CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 Cybersecurity for AI Systems

Head of the Belgian delegation at CEN/CENELEC JTC21.

Co-Convenor of CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG1 Strategic Advisory Group.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Although cybersecurity standardisation for IT and information systems is well advanced in the context of ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27, there are not yet standards applicable to cybersecurity for AI systems. Work has begun within JTC1/SC27 WG4 on ISO/IEC 27090 “Guidance for addressing security threats and failures in artificial intelligence systems”. Furthermore, ISO/IEC will just provide a “guidance” to stakeholders, hence not suitable for demonstration of compliance with EU legislation.

Recital 121 of the AI Act states that standardisation should play a key role to provide technical solutions to providers to ensure compliance with the AI Act, in line with the state-of-the-art, to promote innovation as well as competitiveness and growth in the EU single market. Compliance with harmonised standards, which are normally expected to reflect the state-of-the-art, should be a means for providers to demonstrate conformity with the requirements of the AI Act.

To facilitate compliance by providers, standardisation requests are issued by the European Commission to European Standards Organisations.

The European Commission put forward a Standardisation Request to CEN/CENELEC on 22 May 2023 well in advance of the adoption of the AI Act to allow some lead time for the development of the necessary European standards (ENs).

The AI Act of 13 June 2024 was published in the Official Journal of the EU on 12 July 2024. Hence, the AI Act shall apply from 2nd August 2024. In this context, the standardisation work carried out by CEN/CENELEC JTC21 is bound to have a direct impact on the industry, especially in the field of cybersecurity for AI systems.

The relevance of the proposed standardisation work, in the context of the StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship, is due to the pressing need to have cybersecurity standards for AI systems available and intended to demonstrate compliance with the legal obligations imposed by the AI Act as described below:

Article 15.1 of the AI Act: high-risk AI systems shall be designed and developed in such a way that they achieve an appropriate level of accuracy, robustness, and cybersecurity, and that they perform consistently in those respects throughout their lifecycle.

Article 15.5 of the AI Act: High-risk AI systems shall be resilient against attempts by unauthorised third parties to alter their use, outputs or performance by exploiting system vulnerabilities. The technical solutions aiming to ensure the cybersecurity of high-risk AI systems shall be appropriate to the relevant circumstances and the risks. The technical solutions to address AI specific vulnerabilities shall include, where appropriate, measures to prevent, detect, respond to, resolve and control for attacks trying to manipulate the training data set (data poisoning), or pre-trained components used in training (model poisoning), inputs designed to cause the AI model to make a mistake (adversarial examples or model evasion), confidentiality attacks or model flaws.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Standards and technical reports being drafted either by ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27 or CEN/CENELEC JTC13 may be used as input to the activities of CEN/CENELEC JTC21. However, there is a lack of specific standards covering the field of cybersecurity for AI systems. Hence, the importance of the CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 (Cybersecurity for AI Systems) work towards the development of the necessary European standards (Ens) in the context of the EC standardisation request (SReq#8) on cybersecurity for AI systems.

ISO/IEC JTC1/ SC27 WG4 is progressing the Technical Report ISO/IEC 27090. This deliverable is intended to provide guidance to organisations concerning AI-specific vulnerabilities. Although ISO/IEC 27090 has the potential to become a relevant input, this TR just provides guidance to organisations. Hence, it does not respond to the EC standardisation request.

The actual drafting of European cybersecurity standards for AI systems will be done by CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 over the next 12 months. WG5 kicked-off on 25 January 2024. The New Work Item Proposal (NWIP) on Cybersecurity Specifications for AI Systems was drafted by WG5 and approved by CEN/CENELEC members in August 2024. Consultation on the first Working Draft of the standard will be launched by mid-January 2025, followed by an eventual second consultation in March 2025 and Enquiry by June 2025.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The AI Act highlights the importance of EU harmonised standards and conformity assessment (based on such harmonised standards) for the industrial stakeholders (e.g. providers) and for users of AI systems. Harmonised cybersecurity standards for AI systems need to be developed and adopted, as a matter of urgency, for the benefit of the European industry, including SMEs and startups, as well as users and consumers. In this context, it is necessary to demonstrate the trustworthiness of AI systems. Cybersecurity is one of the many aspects of trustworthiness.

A balanced representation of interests involving all relevant stakeholders in the development of standards, in particular SMEs, consumer organisations and environmental and social stakeholders should therefore be encouraged. My company, FM Tech Consult BV is a Belgium-based SME.

Impact on Society

It is well known that the widespread use of AI systems in many different sectors of the economy is bound to have a significant impact on society. This subject has been debated at length by different academic, industrial, and governmental organisations. Cybersecurity for AI systems, although being just one of the aspects, is essential to demonstrate the trustworthiness of AI systems, hence providing assurance and trust to users and consumers leading to great societal impact.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, initially I advocated two approaches to be followed by JTC21 WG5 simultaneously:

1. "Parallel development" between ISO/IEC SC27 and CEN/CENELEC JTC21 of the technical report ISO/IEC 27090.
2. Drafting a 'homegrown' European Standard (EN) addressing AI-specific vulnerabilities in response to the EC standardisation request in support of the AI Act. Proposed EN title: Cybersecurity Specifications for AI Systems.

However, due to the slow progress within ISO/IEC SC27, now one must rely exclusively on CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 to address AI-specific cybersecurity vulnerabilities in response to the EC standardisation request in support of the AI Act.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Not yet. The actual drafting of a 'homegrown' European Standard (EN) addressing AI-specific vulnerabilities in response to the EC standardisation request in support of the AI Act formally started in September 2024. EN title: Cybersecurity Specifications for AI Systems.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The drafting of the 'homegrown' European standard within JTC21 WG5 on cybersecurity for AI systems. Consultation on the first Working Draft of the standard to be launched by mid-January 2025, followed by an eventual second consultation in March 2025 and Enquiry by June 2025.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.cencenelec.eu/areas-of-work/cen-cenelec-topics/artificial-intelligence/

Enhancing AI Standards for Consumer Protection and Compliance

Christian Grafenauer

AI Expert - Consumer Representative, DIN Verbraucherrat e.V. Germany

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG2 - Artificial Intelligence – Operational Aspects

CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG3 - Artificial Intelligence – Engineering Aspects

CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 - Artificial Intelligence – Cybersecurity

ISO JTC1/SC42 Artificial Intelligence WG1 Foundations

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship has enabled me to submit a contribution on behalf of ANEC to the CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG2 TC EN AI Risk Management System that has been chosen by the experts as a novel approach to a technical risk management system based on a product safety regulation approach. Previous contributions by other experts had to be rejected, since they did not sufficiently address the protection of fundamental rights through safety and trustworthiness as required by the AI Act.

In addition the funding allowed me to join ISO JTC1/SC42 WG1 in order to contribute to the Standard on Logging related to the EC's SR3 (Record Keeping and Logging). I have been officially appointed as an Expert and will shortly begin working on the necessary contributions.

Finally, this fellowship allowed me to join CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 on AI Cybersecurity on behalf of ANEC. ANEC would not have been able to fund this activity without the support of StandICT to sufficiently cover the work done on Cybersecurity. The first meetings of CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 will begin in early Autumn 2024.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship allowed me to contribute and actively engage with the following standards currently developed as a result of the EC's Standardisation Requests:

- ▷ SR1 (Risk Management), SR9 (QMS) and SR10 (AI Conformity Assessment): AI EN Risk Management Standard in CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG2
- ▷ SR2 (Data Quality and Governance), SR6 (Accuracy) and SR7 (Robustness): CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG3 on WG level
- ▷ SR3 (Logging): ISO JTC1/SC42 WG1 on behalf of DIN Verbraucherrat e.V.
- ▷ SR4 (Transparency): FprCEN/CLC ISO/IEC/TS 12791 under adoption through CEN/CENELEC JTC21
- ▷ SR8 (Cybersecurity): CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

These standardisation efforts foster essentially the risk management of SMEs enabling to Streamline AI compliance and integration, reducing regulatory burdens for SMEs. These also improve cybersecurity; while developing robust standards to protect SMEs from AI vulnerabilities. Finally these exchange competitiveness as SMEs' market presence is increased through trustworthy AI systems.

Impact on Society

Consumer Protection is improved with these standards, as they advance consumer rights and safety in AI, building public trust. Also, social Well-being is improved by promoting AI applications in critical sectors like healthcare, enhancing societal benefits.

This activity also supports ethical AI development, aligning with European values for balanced technological progress. These contributions position Europe at the forefront of responsible AI development, benefiting both the economy and society.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to developing new AI standards within CEN/CENELEC and ISO/IEC. My project is specifically targeted at strengthening the protection of fundamental rights in the standards newly developed as direct response to the Standardization request issued to CEN/CENELEC regarding the mandate to develop standards harmonised with the EU AI Act.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to several technical specifications and technical reports regarding the standardisation requests mentioned above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

All standardisation items are developed as planned on their timeline. All standards are scheduled to be published in the OJ of the European union by Q3 2026.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity Standardisation

James Davenport

*Professor of Information Technology, University of Bath
United Kingdom*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC21 Artificial Intelligence WG3 Engineering Aspects
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 AI WG1 Strategic Advisory Group (SAG)
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 AI WG3 Engineering aspects
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 AI WG5 Cybersecurity
ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 Artificial Intelligence Ad Hoc Group 4 (Liaison with SC27 – Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection)
ISO/IEC SC42 WG1 Foundational standards
ISO/IEC SC42 WG3 Trustworthiness
ISO/IEC SC42 JWG5 Joint Working Group ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 - ISO/TC 37 WG: Natural language processing
ISO/IEC SC42 AHG7 JTC1 joint development review
ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection WG 4 Security controls and services

Role

Convener of CEN-CENELEC JTC21 AI WG3 Engineering aspects

Expert member in the other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship supports my standardisation work related to cybersecurity of AI systems. There is currently no standard addressing the cybersecurity of AI systems. In ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG4 27090 is under development; and I contribute directly to this work as I am a member of SC42/AHG4 the 42/27 liaison group. However, this standard will contain no requirements due to the editor's policy. Hence CEN/CENELEC JTC21 needs to develop a Cybersecurity of AI standard with requirements, so I contribute to that, in the ad hoc, and now in WG5. There are many gaps at the technical level, such as accuracy of NLP, accuracy of vision, datasets, bias detection and management, logging etc.), and I convene JTC21 WG3 which looks at these gaps.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In the framework of this fellowship, I am a more effective representative of JTC21/WG3 through funded attendance at SC42. This covers ISO/IEC TR 23281, AWI 23282 (NLP), 24029 series (Robustness), 24970 (logging) and talking about the CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 standards that are relevant. I am liaison from ISO/IEC JTC21 to SC42.

I contributed to JTC21's efficiency by organising the June 2024 Face-to-Face Plenary Meeting in Bath (UK) at a time when no member country of the European Union was actually willing to organise it.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

The EU AI Act places high importance on cybersecurity of AI systems and products, but there is comparatively little work done on this, and none that has reached the level of mature standards. Hence it is important to develop these standards, and ensure that they reflect both the cybersecurity point of view and the specific difficulties of AI, as in the ETSI list, and possibly wider. It is important also to take a holistic view of the risks, as adversaries are not bound by the boundaries we may place between different types of risks and attacks. Hence it will be incumbent on the standardisation leaders to take a wide view, and attend both AI meetings and cybersecurity meetings.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to several new standards on cybersecurity of AI system:

- ▶ ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 standard 27090 “Cybersecurity — Artificial Intelligence — Guidance for addressing security threats and failures in artificial intelligence systems”: contributions in discussions, and a formal N6627, which was accepted (as an Annex rather than a clause).
- ▶ CEN/CENELEC JTC21 NWiP Cybersecurity N177 and N186

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I am working on TR 18115 is likely to be the first deliverable of JTC21: This is causing (at my initiative) a serious debate on the relationship between definitions in the EU AI Act and existing international definitions.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The JTC21 leadership is debating the question TR18115 raises on the relationship between definitions in the EU AI Act and existing international definitions. This is all that stands between TR18115 and publication.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:29:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D#1

Work within the 3GPP SA3-LI, including document handling ahead of and during meetings

Johannes Andersen

Superintendent, Kripos

Norway

Sector

5G and beyond, 6G

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

3GPP SA -Service and System Aspects
WG3 - Security and Privacy, LI - Lawful Interception
ETSI TC - Technical Committee, LI - Lawful Interception

Role

Expert Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The major gap that my contributions address concerns the fact that the majority of participants to the SA3-LI meeting comes from companies delivering either telecom or LI systems hardware and software or from the CSP side. The representation from the law enforcement agencies (LEA) side has been quite low, but in the last couple of years this has improved.

The priority of my contribution is mainly to ensure that the needs that the LEA has will be taken into account when creating and changing the standards. The related challenges concern the fact that the working group is formed by a diverse group of experts who lack either sound technical expertise or background in Law Interception (LI).

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My work within the SA3-LI has mostly been focused on that the changes suggested by others are understandable and that they are an improvement for the LEA community. The standards which are handled within the 3GPP SA3-LI are the following:

3GPP TS 33.106, 3GPP TS 33.107, 3GPP TS 33.108, 3GPP TS 33.126, 3GPP TS 33.127 and 3GPP TS 33.128.

There is also work ongoing with a new technical report 3GPP TR 33.929.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The way the standards evolve could influence SME in the way that if the standards are formed correctly it gives every company equal opportunities to make software and equipment that can communicate with each other. If too much of the development is left up to each company, the complexity could easily lead to something close to monopoly for the big companies. This since they could craft their solutions so that they solely would be able to provide both the hardware and software for the LI/telecom industry.

With clear and open standardisation the possibilities for smaller companies that specialise

themselves in smaller areas can deliver part of the complete solution and also make way for other SME to deliver other parts of the components or software solutions needed within the LI area.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

My project will in cooperation with the rest of the members of the WG produce revised standards. The main focus is on 3GPP TS 33.128.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to technical specifications.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The next work meeting will be hosted in the US in November 2024. We continue working on the technical report and discussion documents related to the standardisation projects.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.3gpp.org/3gpp-groups/service-system-aspects-sa/sa-wg3

Artificial Intelligence - Operational Design Domain for AI systems

Patrick Bezombes

*Independent AI Standardisation Expert
France*

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO-IEC/JTC 1/SC 42 Artificial Intelligence WG3 Trustworthiness

Role

Vice-chair CEN-CENELEC/JTC 21 AI

Convenor JTC 21/WG 1

Chair CEN Workshop on Trusted Data Transaction

Chair Afnor/CN IA

Editor of PWI "Operational design Domain in SC 42/WG 3

Co-editor of JTC 1/WG 13/WD 31303 "Trustworthiness overview and concepts"

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

High-risk AI systems must evolve within defined boundaries, domains and operating conditions. The description of these defined boundaries and operating conditions (sometimes referred to as the operational design domain) is essential to ensure the reliability of AI systems (e.g. with respect to robustness, accuracy, transparency...). To date, many terms are used to refer to these key concepts, without any clear definition or description. There is a consensus that a taxonomy of AI systems' domains and operating conditions is needed. The fellowship proposes a new work topic to address this concern.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I contribute to ISO-IEC/SC 42 (Artificial Intelligence) / WG 3 (Trustworthiness) PWI on the Operational Design Domain for AI systems. This activity supports the EU standardisation Request on AI and aims to clarify key concepts related to trustworthiness characteristics, such as robustness, accuracy, cybersecurity, and transparency.

The contribution highlights the maturity of the topic addressed (Operational Design Domain, domain, operating conditions...), the fact that the notions of the domain, operating conditions and related terms (environment, context...) are largely used in SC 42 deliverables without clear definitions or description, and the fact that there is a specific need for AI systems since this AI systems will self-monitor that they stay within the intended domain of use and within their operating conditions.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

This project will clarify for SMEs when they use standards related to trustworthiness characteristics, as conformity assessment for those characteristics will be done for defined

domains and operating conditions.

Impact on Society

This project is in the context of the AI Act, which aims to protect fundamental rights. For Europe, this project has been initiated by CEN-CENELEC/JTC 21 in support of the European Commission's standardisation request on AI. It is a horizontal project that aims to be adopted and harmonised at the European level.

The impact is potentially significant worldwide, as the European regulation on AI and its subsequent harmonised standards will be followed by any international company that wants to do business in Europe. This project is also targeting verticals that could use the terminology, concepts, and methodology in their own applications.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I lead the project PW1 on the Operational Design Domain for AI systems, where foot 4 on "Domains and operating conditions" will eventually be submitted.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have contributed to a technical report on reference material.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The started activity should be pursued as more than five countries support the project. It is anticipated that form 4, "Domains and operating conditions," will eventually be submitted.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html

AI standardisation in ISO/IEC and CEN/CENELEC on AI verification and validation

Adam Smith

CTO, Standardisation expert, R & D Dragonfly Spain

Sector

Artificial Intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC SC 42 AI WG 1 Foundational standards
ISO/IEC SC 42 AI WG 3 Trustworthiness
ISO/IEC SC 42 AI JWG 2 Joint Working Group ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 42 - ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 7 : Testing of AI-based systems
CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 AI WG 3 Engineering aspects

Role

Expert member and a project editor

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

AI is a rapidly evolving field where trust remains a significant issue. Standards can help engender trust in the supply chain, as well as provide regulatory interoperability. Specifically, there is a gap in the state of the art describing AI bias and testing concepts and requirements and . As an expert in AI testing and bias I am able to drive the targeted standardisation projects forward by building technical consensus as an expert. As an officer my knowledge helps build consensus across the group.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Within the framework of this fellowship, I contribute to three standardisation efforts:

Firstly, I am the project editor for SC 42 WG 1 - ISO/IEC 24970 - AI system logging, parallel development with CEN/CENELEC to support the AI Act in an area with no prior standards work.

Secondly, ISO/IEC SC 42 JWG 2 convenor – Testing of AI systems. Within the group we are working on ISO/IEC TS 29119-11, replacing TR 29119-11. This is the state of the art of AI system testing – which is necessary for conformity assessment.

Thirdly, I am the project editor for SC 42 WG 3 - ISO/IEC 12791 - Treatment of unwanted bias in classification and regression machine learning tasks. This is the first normative work on unwanted bias in ISO/IEC, and is likely to be used by CEN/CENELEC to support the AI Act harmonised standards.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

All three projects are likely to be relevant to the AI Act. SMEs will benefit from clear guidance and societal stakeholders have a voice in the projects. If these projects did not exist, then SMEs would need to rely on lawyers, analysis and academic literature to be compliant.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am contributing to the development of two new ISO/IEC standards on AI systems; ISO/IEC 24970 - AI system logging and ISO/IEC 12791 - Treatment of unwanted bias in classification and regression machine learning tasks. I also contribute revising ISO/IEC TS 29119-11, replacing TR 29119-11.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to technical reports and specifications related to these three standardisation projects.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

All the three standardisation projects are progressing as planned. 12791 is ahead of schedule and may now be published in 2024. 17847 is on track to go to Committee consultation in September 2024. 24970 is on track to go to Committee Draft in October 2024.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

3GPP ITU-R Ad-Hoc Convenor

Giovanni Romano

*3GPP Expert, Novamint Ltd
United Kingdom*

Sector

5G and beyond, 6G

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

3GPP RAN ITU-R Ad-Hoc (3rd Generation Partnership Project, Radio Access Network, International Telecommunication Union – Radiocommunication Ad-Hoc group)
3GPP TSG RAN (3rd Generation Partnership Project Technical Specification Group Radio Access Network), chairing the sessions dedicated to ITU matters
3GPP TSG SA (3rd Generation Partnership Project Technical Specification Group System Aspects)
3GPP PCG (3rd Generation Partnership Project Project Coordination Group)

Role

Convenor of 3GPP RAN ITU-R Ad-Hoc and expert in the other groups.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship addresses four central gaps in the area a future networks:

- ▶ The update of IMT-Advanced (aka 4G) and IMT-2020 (aka 5G) Recommendation
- ▶ The support in the process for the creation of the new Recommendation on IMT-2020 Satellite
- ▶ The definition of the study on radio requirements for 6G
- ▶ Any other topic where ITU-R requests support from 3GPP (e.g., how the 3GPP solutions can support IoT, V2X, emergency calls)

In particular, the activity on IMT-2020 Satellite will provide the regulatory documentation to allow the use of satellite 5G and satellite 5G-IoT solutions in countries that base their Regulations on ITU documents. As such this is a big opportunity for the European industry to influence the satellite technologies, by pushing standard 3GPP technologies against proprietary solutions developed outside Europe

The priority of my activity is the coordination of the 3GPP activities to update the ITU-R Recommendations on IMT-Advanced and IMT-2020. As well as manage the correspondence with ITU-R WP4B officials to define the next steps for the 3GPP submission for inclusion in the new Recommendation on IMT-2020 satellite.

The related challenges are both technical and economic; the technical aspects consist in coordinating the inputs from 3GPP member companies to answer the requests 3GPP received from ITU. Moreover, while the relationship on terrestrial IMT systems between ITU-R WP5D and 3GPP is well established, the relationship with WP4B on satellite IMT systems just started and therefore the definition of the “rules of engagement” is part of my role.

The economic aspects are mainly related to the fact that 3GPP meets all over the world,

which is a big effort for SMEs such as my company, Novamint. From this aspect, the support of StandICT.eu is very important.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship contributes to the 3GPP updates on two ITU-R Recommendations: M.2012 “Detailed specifications of the terrestrial radio interfaces of International Mobile Telecommunications Advanced (IMT-Advanced)” and M.2150 “Detailed specifications of the terrestrial radio interfaces of International Mobile Telecommunications-2020 (IMT-2020).”

More in general, this activity is focusing on Key Enabler 5G and Beyond (6G) with several areas of relevance:

- ▶ 5G satellite: Ensure the standardised 3GPP 5G satellite solutions are included in ITU IMT-2020 Satellite
- ▶ 6G: Contribute to the definition of the activity (workplan, radio requirements) in 3GPP
- ▶ IoT, V2X (others): Coordinate the correspondence between 3GPP and ITU
- ▶ New spectrum: Support the discussion in 3GPP on technical parameters required to identify new bands for IMT and IMT satellite

Satellite communications are a key enabler to provide inclusion by reaching remote areas and ensure safety and communications during disasters. Satellite IoT is also another important market allowing low cost monitoring of goods and environment over the sea or in remote areas, thus fully complementing the terrestrial networks.

It is important that standardised solutions are made available (e.g., via 3GPP) and then made into ITU Recommendations which provide the Regulatory framework for a large number of countries who rely on ITU for these aspects.

In a similar way, ITU published in 2023 the new Recommendation ITU-R M.[IMT.FRAMEWORK FOR 2030 AND BEYOND]: Framework and overall objectives of the future development of IMT for 2030 and beyond. This document is the baseline for the definition of the requirements of IMT-2030, aka 6G. 3GPP is defining its work plan to contribute to the definition of technical solutions for 6G.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

European SMEs started to be quite active in 3GPP with the specification work of 5G, especially on aspects relevant to Verticals. In particular, SMEs are quite active in IMT-2020 satellite aspects and can benefit from the inclusion of 3GPP solutions in global standards defined by ITU.

Impact on Society

Satellite communications are a key enabler to provide inclusion by reaching remote areas and ensure safety and communications during disasters. Satellite IoT is also another important market allowing low cost monitoring of goods and environment over the sea or in remote areas, thus fully complementing the terrestrial networks.

It is important that standardised solutions are made available (e.g., via 3GPP) and then made into ITU Recommendations which provide the Regulatory framework for a large number of countries who rely on ITU for these aspects. The availability of open standards is also providing economies of scale, thus lowering the cost for the end users.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to the 3GPP updates on two ITU-R Recommendations: M.2012 “Detailed specifications of the terrestrial radio interfaces of International Mobile Telecommunications Advanced (IMT-Advanced)” and M.2150 “Detailed specifications of the terrestrial radio interfaces of International Mobile Telecommunications-2020 (IMT-2020).”

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have drafted the technical report on the revision of the concerned standards, and these have been submitted to the 3GPP RAN ITU-R Ad-Hoc.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The revision contributions have been submitted, and are under approval by PCG, due in September 2024. Further contributions on IMT-2020 satellite are in progress to be submitted at 3GPP TSG RAN in September.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.3gpp.org/3gpp-groups/radio-access-networks-ran/ran-ah1>

Participation in SA6 to support CAPIF Guidelines from ETSI OpenCAPIF

David Artuñedo Guillén

*Head of Future Networks Lab, Telefónica I+D. S.A.u.
Spain*

Sector

5G and beyond, 6G

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

3GPP SA6 Application Enablement and Critical Communication Applications
ETSI OpenCAPIF SDG

Role

Chair of OpenCAPIF in ETSI and expert member in 3GPP

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The Common API Framework (CAPIF) defined by 3GPP started in Release 15. This API framework enables the secure exposure of APIs in 5G Networks and it has been adopted to expose Network Exposure Function (NEF) APIs, EDGEAPP, SEAL and VEAL, ... Although the definition of CAPIF started in Release 15, the lack of Open implementations has limited the adoption of CAPIF in Research communities. Open CAPIF, an ETSI SDG, has come to fill this GAP doing an open implementation of CAPIF in Release 17 flavour, but there is still a GAP on how to use CAPIF. That's why in Release 19, the TR 23.946 is describing the Guidelines to use CAPIF, and these guidelines are being produced based on the work from OpenCAPIF SDG providing real examples of CAPIF in action.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

CAPIF Guidelines are in TR 23.946 as part of Release 19 of 3GPP. These guidelines are critical for CAPIF adoption by European companies. These guidelines are the perfect complement to the brand new announced OpenCAPIF ETSI software group, that is delivering an Open Source CAPIF implementation for European companies to use.

In the framework of this fellowship, my contribution as OpenCAPIF Chair is to bring practical examples of CAPIF usage to TR 23.946. This contribution has materialised in contributions accepted in SA6 Meeting in Rotterdam in August 2024 and published already in TR 23.946 version 0.6.0.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

By adopting CAPIF, following the guidelines that will be created in SA6, European companies will increase their competitiveness making better products, easier to deploy over 5G Networks, improving their interoperability with commercial solutions from vendors that support CAPIF.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

My contribution has a direct impact in 3GPP Release 19 specifications in the TR 23.946 CAPIF Guidelines.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have contributed to the technical report named here above. In addition, I have presented the work in two webinars that are openly available ETSI webinars for MEC³ and Open CAPIF Release 1⁴.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

There are some contributions already integrated in TR 23.946 version 0.6.0 in sections 6.3, 6.4 and 6.8. Contributions will continue towards the end of year, targeting next SA6 3GPP meetings in India (#63) and USA (#64)

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.3gpp.org/3gpp-groups/service-system-aspects-sa/sa-wg6>

 <https://ocf.etsi.org/>

³ <https://www.brighttalk.com/service/player/en-US/theme/default/channel/12761/webcast/612087/play?b=71987&embedUrl=https://www.etsi.org/events/webinars>

⁴ <https://www.brighttalk.com/service/player/en-US/theme/default/channel/12761/webcast/619594/play?b=71987&embedUrl=https://www.etsi.org/events/webinars>

Standardisation Working Group for Quantum Interconnect

Richard Pitwon
Consultant, Resolute Photonics UK Ltd
United Kingdom

Sector

Quantum Technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEC Technical Committee 86 – Fibre Optics
IEC SC86B - Fibre optic interconnecting devices and passive components
IEC TC86 JWG9 - Optical functionality for electronic assemblies
BSI GEL 86 – Fibre Optics
BSI GEL86/2 - Fibre optic interconnecting devices and passive components
BSI ICT/1/1/2 – Quantum Technologies
ISO/IEC Joint Technical Committee 3 – Quantum Technologies

Role

Head of UK IEC TC86 delegation and SC86B chair
Chair of IEC SC86B, BSI GEL 86 and BSI GEL86/2
Secretary of IEC TC86 JWG9
Expert member of BSI ICT/1/1/2 and ISO/IEC JTC3

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The formation in 2024 of the ISO/IEC Joint Technical Committee on Quantum Technologies is providing the most far-reaching body for quantum standards development covering the full range of quantum technologies across the pillars of quantum communication, quantum computation and quantum sensing, metrology and imaging. However the scope of JTC3 excludes fibre optics explicitly citing IEC TC86. This represents a huge gap in standardisation of the most mainstream aspects of quantum technologies, in particular quantum scalable networks for secure communication, photonic quantum computing and quantum sensing and imaging require a robust standards eco-system for fibre optic and photonic components.

Europe must position itself as a world-leader in quantum networks and computation. On my fellowship project, the main priority is therefore to prepare a proposal for formation of a new IEC TC86 working group for Quantum Interconnect, which covers all aspects of passive and active optical interconnect for quantum technologies, engage with National Committees to secure support for the proposal and to present proposal at IEC TC86 general meeting and plenary.

The main challenge is that the UK and EU are currently leading the world in quantum science, however commercial realisation of that knowledge continues to be hindered by the fact that many companies that have the capabilities required for elements of the quantum interconnect supply chain do not frequently collaborate. Consequently, EU and UK developers must seek out bespoke solutions from a fragmented ecosystem or take advantage of more

responsive/coherent offerings available outside of the EU. While the industrial aspects of these challenges are being addressed by EU and UK collaborative R&D initiatives, it will be particularly critical for EU companies to influence and develop international standardisation of quantum technologies.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

On this fellowship project, I have prepared a formal proposal for formation of a new IEC TC86 working group (WG10) for Quantum Interconnect, which covers all aspects of passive and active optical interconnect for quantum technologies. I will formally present this proposal at the IEC TC86 plenary in November 2024. I have engaged with key members of other National Committees including Netherlands, Canada, Belgium, Germany and the USA to secure support for the proposal. I am progressing “IEC TR 63568-1: ED1: Quantum Interconnect - Part 1: Introduction and roadmap for standardisation” to the Approval Stage on this fellowship project. Also, I have given the following two international talks in the last six months introducing the IEC TR 63568-1.

I have also co-organised the 10th International Symposium on Optical Interconnect in Data Centres, which will take place at ECOC 2024 in Frankfurt and will include quantum talks by European companies. Furthermore, I am the general chair of the Optica British and Irish Conference in Optics and Photonics (BICOP 2024), which will be held in IET London in mid-December 2024 and includes a full day of quantum sessions.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The formation of a new IEC working group on fibre optic quantum interconnect will align with the technologies of many European SMEs who would benefit from early engagement to develop standards, which help accelerate commercial adoption of their approaches. Therefore, I am strongly engaging with European quantum SMEs to secure support for the proposal and encourage participation. The successful formation of the WG would be followed by the establishment of liaisons to ISO/IEC JTC3 and CEN/CENELEC TC86.

Impact on Society

Europe is already a world-leader in the scientific research and industrialisation of quantum technologies, especially with regards to quantum communication and quantum computation technologies. My fellowship will strengthen European influence on quantum standards and by assuming a strong position on quantum technologies from industrial, academic and standardisation angles, Europe will be in a stronger position to establish a global competitive edge in this field.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am drafting a technical report; IEC TR 63568-1: ED1: Quantum Interconnect - Part 1: Introduction and roadmap for standardisation” and it contains a roadmap for new standards to be pursued in the new working group if approved. These include:

- 1) Quantum grade optical connectors - Optical connectors with lower insertion loss and higher return loss. It is anticipated this will continue with multiple grades emerging as fibre and ferrule manufacturing and termination practices continue to improve.
- 2) Quantum grade optical fibres - Optical fibres with lower attenuation. In addition to incremental improvements in fibre manufacture, this will include emerging novel specialist fibres such as hollow core fibres, which have been reported to have lower loss than conventional optical fibre.
- 3) Low-loss, high isolation passive optical routers - Passive wavelength splitting components, such as AWGs with reduced crosstalk between branches and lower insertion loss.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, this fellowship will result in the formal decision by IEC TC86 on the proposal for new TC86/WG10 on Quantum Interconnect at the TC86 plenary in October 2024.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The IEC TR 63568-1: ED1: Quantum Interconnect - Part 1: Introduction and roadmap for standardisation" will be revised in response to comments received during CD circulation. This will result in the updated CDV version of this TR.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:7:712365770157399:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1279,25

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/10138914.html>

Standardizing the Quantum Internet

Marcello Caleffi

Assistant Professor, University of Naples Federico II
Italy

Sector

Quantum Technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IETF Quantum Internet Research Group

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The Quantum Internet is set to transform ICT by enabling applications such as Distributed Quantum Computing (DQC) and secure communications that have no classical counterparts. Significant strides have been made in Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) networks, as shown by the ETSI ISG in QKD. However, while QKD offers private key generation for classical encryption, it remains a preliminary use of quantum information in networking, highlighting the need for a standardised classical-quantum interface. This interface is crucial for integrating Quantum Networks (QNs) with the existing Internet infrastructure.

Unlike QKD, which relies on physical qubit transmission, the Quantum Internet and its key applications like DQC use entanglement as the main communication resource. Entanglement enables qubit transmission without particle movement, enabling protocols like teleportation. However, communication depletes the entangled pairs, necessitating constant regeneration. Managing entanglement generation and distribution is essential, requiring precise coordination between network nodes. Currently, this depends on classical signalling, which lacks standardised protocols for a quantum-classical interface. Therefore, creating classical protocols for entanglement is a key priority in QN development.

Another challenge lies in determining the benefits of a distinct classical control plane for QNs. The IETF Quantum Internet Research Group (RFC 9340) has acknowledged the separation of quantum and classical data plans, but the relationship between their control planes remains uncertain. Defining the role of a classical control plane for QNs is a critical issue.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowships seek to bridge the gap in the standardisation of the classical-quantum interface, define the classical control plane's benefits, and prioritise the development of classical signalling protocols for managing entanglement. Hence, my project aims at defining the quantum counterpart of the classical Internet Protocol, defined within IETF RFC 791 standard and following standards within IETF Quantum Internet Research Group.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on the Society

The adoption of standardised classical communication protocols significantly accelerates the scalability of quantum networks. As quantum technologies advance, the ability to seamlessly

integrate new quantum devices into existing networks becomes crucial. Standardised protocols provide a foundation for the consistent and reliable integration of diverse quantum resources, paving the way for the widespread adoption of quantum technologies across various applications and industries.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to developing new standards on the quantum counterpart of the classical Internet Protocol, defined within IETF RFC 791 standard and following standards.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to the development of the standard project documents within IETG QIRG.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The main progress of my activity is centred around our participation in the IETF 121 meeting in Dublin, scheduled for November 2024. Until then, our efforts have focused on engaging with IETF QIRG members to foster collaboration and align our work with the broader goals of quantum network standardisation. This includes the preparation of a slide presentation for dissemination at the meeting, which highlights advancements in quantum network design and addresses key challenges such as entanglement management and the classical-quantum interface. These contributions will support ongoing discussions and shape future standards in quantum communication.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/qirg/about/>

Actively contribute to ISO/IEC/JTC 1/SC38 and IEEE S2ESC to harmonize Cloud and DevOps standards

Ruth Lennon

Lecturer, Atlantic Technological University
Ireland

Sector

Cloud and Edge Computing

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

NSAI SC11 Cloud & Distributed Systems working group
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7 Software and Systems Engineering
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 29 Agile and DevOps
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC38 Cloud Computing and Distributed Platforms
the IEEE Standards Authority for Strategic and Emerging Standards
Committee (S2ESC)

Role

Chair of the NSAI SC11 Cloud & Distributed Systems working group.

Editor of the new IEEE 2675-2 Observability across DevOps standard.

Secretary of IEEE P828 and the vice-chair of IEEE P730.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

There is a notable gap in DevOps standardisation in the area of observability, and reliability particularly in the development of cloud computing and distributed platforms created using coded formats. Interestingly, many of the existing standards that involve software development quality procedures have failed to include participation of systems experts. This can lead to a lack of understanding of how the standards can be applied in the creation of infrastructure as code to support evolving areas of AI and Data Spaces.

A strong priority for this work is to contribute to standards to enable consideration of the support for data management in the cloud. Data spaces can only be fully realised with the application of strong quality management controls through standardisation at multiple levels. Standardisation of quality management practices, monitoring and observability for data management in cloud computing and big data, is key to the prevention of unforeseen legal and ethical risks related to use of multisource data, data from the edge, and as used in AI applications. SC 38s work on ISO/IEC AWI 20996 on continuity resilience and ISO/IEC 19274 on Edge and networking are just 2 work items that are essential ground items for modern concepts. Both areas of Cloud computing and distributed platforms (SC 38), and software development (SC 7) as considered in DevOps are essential supports for dataspace, data management in Big Data and AI.

The main challenge to effective implementation of standards in this area is enhanced communications regarding planned work, work in progress and published standards. Regular and enhanced communications between the ISO, IEC and IEEE is essential to ensure a unified standards roadmap across all three bodies moving forward. Europe needs to continue the harmonisation of standards across standards bodies in evolving areas such as software development for cloud hosted or cloud enabled technologies.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

It is critical to establish common European standards linking hardware and software particularly in new areas of technology & standardisation. Irish national input comes from companies Google, Microsoft and Huawei etc.; Enterprise Ireland (national agency) and research centres. European priorities of reliability and environment impact need to be clearly established in SC 38. Example use cases include the improvement of reliability of edge and cloud computing where processing of personal data, or highly regulated data is concerned. In chairing my national mirror body committee meetings I coordinate the response of our members to standards.

In the framework of this fellowship, I chose to promote greater awareness of and adoption of Cloud, and Cloud hosted software based standards due to a unified strategy for DevOps and Cloud standards both at JTC 1/SC 38 and IEEE S2ESC level. As a first stage in this process I have been working with the IEEE S2ESC to create a strategy to promote standards through the website. We have now devised a template which we are using to establish a unified view of standards with each standard due to have its own page. This page will contain information about the timeline for the standards and an explanation of how the standards are relevant. The outline design is approved and now we are in the information gathering stage. We expect pages to be built over the month of September.

I promote DevOps for cloud computing software (eg. Configuration of switches, servers, IoT and edge devices) related sustainability and reliability. This has been achieved through contributions to standards meetings in IEEE 2675-1 for Systems Reliability and the new IEEE 2675-2 DevOps Observability for which I am the editor. I participate in the CEN Focus Group on 'Data, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge' to bring this information back to the national body SC 11 committee to enable expertise from various domains to be brought to the discussion on cloud based standards.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Contribution to the national body position through discussions with our members provides a voice to the concerns or challenges of our SMEs as well as to larger organisations.

Impact on Society

As a national body we have members contributing to the CEN Focus Group on 'Data, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge'. We feel this is important as the cloud supports data and dataspace whilst at the same time data is utilised in supporting the cloud. This could have a large impact on standards created in the near future. Obtaining expert advice from many areas is important in this early stage of these standards.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes; the IEEE 2675-2 Observability for DevOps PAR was created alongside this proposal with the goal of contributing to the standard development throughout this period. The PAR was accepted and the early stage of searching for members has now commenced.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Another clear deliverable was the promotion of standards. This can be seen through the development of the S2ESC website which is now progressing from the early design over the last two months to information gathering for display on the website. It is hoped to have the first version of the website available at the end of September.

Other contributions to standards did not result in technical reports but did involve contributions to standards as part of working group meetings.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The meeting in Dublin for the local mirror committee has occurred already. Highlighting of standards is currently in progress. Contributions to standards at meetings are ongoing. The second significant part of my contribution involved attendance at the ISO/IEC/JTC 1/SC38 Plenary to be held in London in September 2024.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.nsai.ie/standards/sectors/ict-standards/

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/45086.html>

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/601355.html>

EU Data Act - Evaluation and filling of standardisation gaps to satisfy technical provisions of it

Joachim Koss

*Independent principal consultant, JK Consulting and Projects
Germany*

Sector

Internet of things

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI Technical Committee SmartM2M

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With this fellowship, I support manufacturers and service providers of connected products or related services to select the sufficient standards for being compliant to the new Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 (European Data Act). This shall ensure that users of a connected products or related services in the EU can access, in a timely manner, the data generated by the use of that connected products or related services and that those users can use the data, including by sharing them with third parties of their choice.

The challenges are to identify gaps, to address them in relevant SDOs (particularly ETSI/ oneM2M) and to disseminate and inform stakeholders of relevant industry areas about already existing standards and current work on standards, which they may apply in order for their products being compliant to the new Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 (European Data Act).

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship contributes to analysing the ICT (IoT) Standards landscape in order to find gaps to be filled by future standardisation work and also to identify existing standards, which manufacturers and service providers of connected products or related services may apply in order for their products being compliant to the new Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 (European Data Act).

Some examples of ICT standards being relevant for the Data Act:

- ▶ ETSI EN 303 760: "SAREF Guidelines for IoT Semantic Interoperability"
- ▶ ETSI TS 103 264: "SmartM2M; Smart Applications; Reference Ontology and oneM2M Mapping"
- ▶ ETSI TS 103 410-x: "SmartM2M; Extension to SAREF; Part x ..."
- ▶ ETSI TS 103 673: "SmartM2M; SAREF Development Framework and Workflow, Streamlining the Development of SAREF and its Extensions".
- ▶ ETSI TS 103 780: "SmartM2M; SAREF: oneM2M usage guidelines"

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The Data Act applies to the group of holders of data (not only but also SMEs) acting on the European market irrespective of the place of establishment of those manufacturers and providers.

Impact on Society

Since the addressed existing or to be developed standards enable particularly semantic interoperability across the IoT, they also provide cross domain and cross-vendor IoT semantic interoperability for exchanging data with common understanding of its meaning. This will become increasingly important as greater quantities of data are generated and shared across the IoT. It opens new market opportunities in the domains of e.g. Healthcare, Smart Grid, Smart Metering, Intelligent Transport Systems, Industrial Automated Systems, and Smart Cities, which depend on collecting and processing data. With that, it directly supports the strong European goal of the "digital single market".

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

No, for the moment this work focuses on establishing a gap analysis.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I draft a gap analysis report that will be published and disseminated for stakeholders.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I have initiated a special meeting of ETSI TC SmartM2M dealing with the Data Act, which took place in May 2024. I contributed a presentation giving a summary about the Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 (European Data Act) with the focus on technical aspects. This one provided the basis for my second contribution, which was an initial draft of a gap analysis.

The next step will be publishing the gap analysis report and sharing the key findings with the stakeholders.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.etsi.org/committee/smartm2m>

IoT Semantic Interoperability for Internet of Robotic Things

Amelie Gyrard

*Principal Research & Innovation Consultant, Trialog
France*

Sector

Internet of things

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Within this fellowship, I work on the IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots, which contributes to the ICT standardisation rolling plan 2024 in the area of Robotics and Autonomous Systems.

My involvement in ISO/TC 299 Robotics and IEEE Robotics Standards contributes to the following actions:

- ▶ Action 1: Ensure coordination of standardisation efforts on robotics and autonomous systems in Europe, promoting interaction of all stakeholders, taking into account their vision and real needs (e.g., through public-private partnerships), while engaging on an international level to lead and export the EU's objectives.
- ▶ Action 4: Standards should be developed to define the main characteristics for all levels of the interaction from mechanical to electrical to protocol to semantic levels, between robot and tool, to ensure the exchangeability and to enable the design of generic tooling (plug-and-play). There are 2 main types of End Effector. "Off-the-Shelf" and "bespoke". It is desirable that off-the-shelf end effectors operate on a single software protocol. There is a need for Industry 4.0 to standardise this. It would then become Plug-&-Play. For "Bespoke" end effectors (most commonly purchased) the system integrator specifies the software protocol for the Robot and End Effector.

In the area of Internet of Things, my contributions in the framework of this fellowship contribute to the following actions:

- ▶ Action 2: SDOs to continue ongoing work in the area of semantic standards for better data interoperability.
- ▶ Action 5: Promote the development and foster the adoption of the international Reference Architecture for IoT developed in ISO/IEC JTC 1 SC41.

And moreover, related to Artificial Intelligence, I support:

- ▶ Action 2: SDOs should coordinate their efforts on AI standardisation in Europe and internationally, especially ISO/IEC JTC 1 SC 42
- ▶ Action 5: Within the AI4EU initiative, identify leading open source activities which complement standardisation work and analyse to what extent they respond to EU requirements. Where useful, establish dialogue, liaisons, or partnerships with such open-source projects.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship covers my participation in monthly meetings for IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots, with the possibility to share presentations. Also, there are also additional technical meetings. I draft contributions to IEEE Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots (e.g., IEEE RAM). In addition, I draft contributions to Landscape and Gap Analysis For Robotics Collaboration between Adra-e & StandICT.eu 2026, which will be shortly published.

Moreover, the objective of my fellowship is to include European contributions on viable methodologies for semantic interoperability in ISO standards: ISO SC41 IoT and Digital Twin, with a focus on practical use cases in the domains of the Internet of Robotic Things.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Trialog is a SME so we are directly impacted by my contribution. Trialog was the coordinator of the ACCRA H2020 project (robots for ageing), which is now finished. We follow up with standard activities on robotics. In addition, the standards under consideration will benefit all the Smart Robotics and Internet of Robotic Things ecosystem, including SMEs. SME can develop tools and applications compliant with those standards.

Impact on Society

Accelerating the use of digital twins, as the existence of the semantic repository allows the digital twin to manage semantics while the physical twin is managing data. This methodology will ensure a consistent continuum between the physical twin and the digital twin.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to the creation of a new standard; IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to drafting use cases for the standard in development.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The standard won't be officially released before 2026, so that is a lot of work to be done before its publication.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1872.3/11037/>

IoT identification standardisation

Josef Preishuber-Pflügl

CEO, innoveer e.U.

Austria

Sector

Internet of things

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1 SC31 Automatic identification and data capture techniques WG4 Radio communications

Role

Convener ISO/IEC JTC1 SC31 WG4 Radio Communications

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With this fellowship I work on RFID (UHF RFID, RAIN RFID) that is a major used technology for the supply chain and production to reduce overproduction and waste. Furthermore, it is a technology for the Digital Product Passport, which is strongly supported by the European Commission for sustainable product regulations⁵. Different from QR-Code passive RFID offers reading of information as e.g. DPP content without line of sight with multiple of hundred reads per second over short distance, but also over a distance of up to 20 metres. As it is passive RFID, this means that the microwatts for powering the chip on the label that holds IoT or DPP information is derived from the RF field and there is no need for a battery. For that reason RFID is a key technology for the European Union and in particular for the DPP and IoT. In order to ensure the usability and proper performance, it is important to work on the air interfaces and related test standards. This is part of this project in order to bring in the new European demand into these standards. Stepping in is for the benefit of a continuous progress and shall bridge the gap to ensure that the important work is continued with the educated expert and that in future a different solution is found.

My fellowship contributes to the continuation activity within ISO/IEC JTC1 SC31 WG4 “Radio communications” work to serve the international and European industry and society to enhance standards to better serve the needs of Europe and the whole world and in particular to provide standards that are in particular relevant for IoT and DPP.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Within the framework of the funded fellowship, I am the project editor of ISO/IEC 18000-63, contributing to the progress of ISO/IEC 18000-63, and also for, ISO/IEC 18000-6, ISO/IEC 18047-63, ISO/IEC 29167, ISO/IEC 19823.

The framing existing standards are the following:

- ▶ ISO/IEC 18000 63, Information technology — Radio frequency identification for item management — Part 63: Parameters for air interface communications at 860 MHz to 960 MHz Type C
- ▶ ISO/IEC 18000 6, Information technology — Radio frequency identification for item management — Part 6: Parameters for air interface communications at 860 MHz to 960

⁵ https://hadea.ec.europa.eu/calls-proposals/digital-product-passport_en

MHz General

- ▷ ISO/IEC 18047-6, Information technology — Radio frequency identification device conformance test methods — Part 6: Test methods for air interface communications at 860 MHz to 960 MHz
- ▷ ISO/IEC 18047-63, Information technology — Radio frequency identification device conformance test methods — Part 63: Test methods for air interface communications at 860 MHz to 960 MHz
- ▷ ISO/IEC 29167 (multiple parts), Information technology — Automatic identification and data capture techniques
- ▷ ISO/IEC 19823 (multiple parts), Information technology — Conformance test methods for security service crypto suites

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

SMEs are major contributors in the RFID industry, contributing to in particular tags, readers and system integration. All of them require harmonised standards. Therefore, the work and content of ISO/IEC 18000-63 is very important to them.

Impact on Society

This activity is the continuation of the ISO/IEC JTC1 SC31 WG4 “Radio communications” work to serve the international and European industry and society to enhance standards to better serve the needs of Europe and the whole world and in particular to provide standards that are in particular relevant for IoT and DPP.

RFID (UHF RFID, RAIN RFID) are a major used technology for the supply chain and production to reduce overproduction and waste. Furthermore, it is a technology for the Digital Product Passport, which is strongly supported by the European Commission for sustainable product regulations.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to the revision of ISO/IEC 18000-63

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, contribute drafting technical reports regarding the revision of ISO/IEC 18000-63.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The work on the revision of ISO/IEC 18000-63 has been approved by ISO already in 2023. However, the decision on the key changes were delayed until early 2024. Later then it was recognized that the previous working document had disappeared, meaning it was no longer editable as Word document, by ISO and any reasonable editing was prevented. So additional effort had to be spent in order to move the document into the new ISO OSD system. This is now operational and work can proceed.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/45332.htm

3. Innovation for Digital Single Market

■ ISO TC 307 Working Group 5 - Governance

Belen Suarez

*Convenor, Reacción Económica
Spain*

Sector

Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO TC 307 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies, WG5
Governance
ISO TC 307 -WG 3 Smart Contracts
ISO TC 307 CAG 1
ISO TC 307 AG1- SBP Review Advisory Group
ISO TC AHG 4- Carbon Market Creation
ISO TC 307 AG 3 Digital Currencies
CEN/CENELEC JTC 19 Blockchain and DLT WG2 Environmental
Sustainability for Blockchain and DLT

Role

Convenor at ISO TC 307 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies, WG5 Governance

Convenor at CEN/CENELEC JTC 19 Blockchain and DLT WG2 Environmental Sustainability for Blockchain and DLT

Expert in other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Blockchain and DLTs have a significant potential value proposition to promote the integrity of data, trust and confidence however, the technology as a whole is facing the “Valley of Death” of innovation, it is still interesting for the future however it lacks market attraction. It is due to several reasons, among them the lack of trust in the governance models of the applications is one of the fundamental bottlenecks.

Blockchain carries certain limitations and risks, some of which are specific to Blockchain while others are relevant to digital technologies more broadly, for instance, risks relating to privacy and security, custody of access credentials, and cryptography vulnerabilities.

To exploit the value proposition of Blockchain and DLT and manage risks to deliver responsible innovation and adoption the governance frameworks of Blockchains and their applications must be transparent and clearly defined, consistent with legal and regulatory obligations. Hence, developing standards at the global level for governance is a key priority for Blockchain and DLT development.

Finally, to establish standards to provide guidance and requirements creating a common framework and language to build trust and allow interoperability and integrity of networks and solutions, however it is needed to face the diversity of the approaches, the high degree of creativity in the networks design and the lack of validation proofs for most of them. Among the documents in development under the ISO TC 307-WG5 two fundamental areas are currently running, firstly one related to Blockchain systems auditing guidelines and the second regarding the governance of DAOs.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation calls for standardisation in several areas to enable mature governance models to interact with each other but also with centralised systems. This work is in line with several European proposals, including the Markets in Cryptoassets Regulation (MiCA) as part of its “Digital Finance package”; Regulation (EU) 2022/2554 on digital operational resilience for the financial sector (Digital Operational Resilience Act, or DORA); the establishment of a framework for a European Digital Identity” (eIDAS2) introducing a new trust service for electronic ledgers, and the European Digital Identity Portfolio (EUDI), a means of identification for European natural and legal persons based on Sovereign Identity principles.

The standardisation request of the Rolling Plan in Action 1 states “The standardisation community should further analyse potential standardisation gaps and identify solutions to fill them, also taking into account other chapters of the Standardization Rolling Plan, including actions and references to Blockchain and DLT and their applications”, and explicitly includes activities focused on governance.

With the support of this fellowship, I am contributing to the following projects:

- 1.ISO/WD TS 23353 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies – Auditing Guidelines
- 2.ISO/NWIP Governance for DAO

In addition, this work could be very relevant also for the following projects:

- ▶ CEN/CENELC TR JTC19003 Environmental and Sustainability Classification Methodology of consensus mechanism of Blockchain and DLTs.
- ▶ CEN/CENELEC JTC19-WG2 on a new work item proposal (NWIP) for the technical specification (TS) - Environmental and Sustainability Taxonomy of Blockchain and DLT Applications

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Despite the fact that 95% of industries are composed of SMEs, there is a significant underrepresentation of this organisation’s viewpoint on standards development. I am the liaison officer of the Small Business Standards in all the TCs at ISO. I contribute to giving a voice to European SMEs in standardisation at the European and international levels. In addition, to provide comments in the meetings I promote the use of the compatibility test of the SBS and collaborate in the workshops to facilitate the mutual understanding among the industry and the SDOs.

Impact on Society

These standardisation efforts support the achievement of the objectives of the Green Deal and the SDGs, as well as the political objectives of the European Commission and support for the New European Standardization Strategy. As a convenor position of a key working group at the ISO level, I am able to promote the European values in standards development. In addition, this action promotes the improvement in the efficiency of public services with the use of reliable applications and technologies that contribute to sustainable development.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to the development of two standardisation projects, including ISO/WD TS 23353 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies – Auditing Guidelines as well as ISO/NWIP Governance for DAO.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Not directly; as the convenor, my contribution is supported by the administrative management of the ISO TC 307 WG-5 Governance, in activities such as the publication of agendas, meetings, and list of attendance and collaboration with other TC convenors to allow a fruitful collaboration and avoid overloading.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The Convenorship of my working group is an ongoing activity that I will pursue beyond the ending of this fellowship.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/6266604.html

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2702172&cs=148F2B917E4B67BCFD6FE36CE0EA923AC

Develop an ISO Technical Report standard on innovative new & emerging DLT/Blockchain Use Cases

Caroline Thomas
Independent IT Consultant
Greece

Sector

Blockchain

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies

Role

Convenor in ISO/ TC 307 WG6 use cases

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The gap is to develop use cases that reflect new and emerging applications and technologies applied by DLT/Blockchain, to inform development of ISO standards.

The key challenge is to respond to market and regulatory demands for new global and European technical standards. A series of new regulations in 2024-25 (eg: cyber resilience, AI Acts, EiDAS), and European Sustainability Reporting Standards (eg. International climate laws and CSRD & ESRS) can be facilitated by the innovation in Web 3 evolution and the latest research of DLT/Blockchain technologies, including new decentralised business models and innovative products.

The priorities for new use cases in DLT/blockchain technologies today is innovation in the data economy, Web 3, and the fast-growing global environment of new decentralised business models with safeguards for security and e-privacy (eg: DeFi - digital currencies, tokenization / Sustainability - DLT carbon markets & smart energy / Health / Metaverse / NFTs etc) and interoperable systems with Artificial Intelligence (AI) internet of things etc (eg: digital product passports, medical data) and blockchain consortiums (eg: EBSI/BCN etc).

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship aims to contribute to the ICT landscape by progressing the approved new work item to develop an ISO Technical Report on ISO/TR 24878 New and emerging DLT/Blockchain Use Cases.

The ICT Standards I am dealing with build across 2 international standards on use cases already published from ISO/TC 307 WG6, a WG that I convene:

- ▷ ISO/TR 3242:2023 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies – Use Cases Summary, for which I am the project Leader and co-editor.
- ▷ ISO/TR 6039: 2023 - Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies-Identifiers of subjects and objects for the design of blockchain systems
- ▷ ISO/TR 6277: 2024 -Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies –Data flow model for blockchain and DLT use cases <https://www.iso.org/standard/82158.html>

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The contribution impacts European SMEs and/or European societies and decision-makers on a high level by developing technical standards in DLT/Blockchain that reflect European democratic values including.

- E-Privacy: EU Artificial Intelligence Act, new Data Act, GDPR
- Fintech and Def: MiCA crypto
- Sustainable initiatives: carbon markets, smart energy
- Interoperable platforms: EBSI, digital product passports

Moreover, I see two major impacts with SMEs. Firstly, international standards enable faster technical adoption for SMEs, as ISO standards provide 'templates' of technical systems and guidelines, that provide a baseline for SMEs to build their own solutions that are interoperable and lower risk for potential partners/investors.

Secondly, SME are involved in standards development: The use case methodology in ISO/TC 307 WG6 is based on active outreach to SMEs who are pioneering new DLT capabilities. They provide contributions to the standards through ISO/TC 307 WG6 and ongoing external business events

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am leading the work developing the new standard ISO/TR 24878 New and emerging DLT/Blockchain Use Cases.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contributed to drafting the technical report, ISO/TR 24878 New and emerging DLT/Blockchain Use Cases.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The new standard ISO/TR 24878 New and emerging DLT/Blockchain Use Cases, approved at the ISO/TC 307 Plenary in November 2023. And from the start of this fellowship, in June 2024, there has been progress to source new use cases, generated from the ISO/TC 307 Plenary in June 2024 in Spain.

As Convenor of this WG the progress, I've hosted two WG6 meetings to demonstrate new use cases during the Plenary for WG6 members and guests. These meetings hosted 12 different use case proposals, by European and international presenters from SMEs and organisations. This informed WG6 members of new and emerging applications and trends, and created a short list for use cases for the new AWI:TR24878 Also, the WG6 Use Case template has been issued and drafting has started for the new standard.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/6266604.html

4. Sustainable Growth

Contribute to the Formal Draft of EN ISO 16757-5

Pierre-François Jullien

CEO, Atalane

France

Sector

Construction Building Information Modelling

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN TC 442 Building Information Modelling (BIM)/WG2 Exchange information
EN ISO 12006-3, EN ISO 23386, EN ISO 23387

Role

Expert Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

There is a growing need for information about building services systems during the planning and design of buildings. The designers in building services have to execute detailed calculations and simulations to ensure saving of energy and to satisfy hygienic and comfort criteria in heating, ventilation, air conditioning, and sanitary plants. They have to provide better and better documentation to verify the compliance with these requirements. The resulting designs have to describe the complete plants without internal interference or intersection with the building.

These requirements can only be achieved with modern engineering applications like CAD- and CAE-systems, calculation programs, BIM tools, and management software.

Nearly all big manufacturers provide their own software (mostly for free) as electronic catalogues to select, to design, and to calculate their products. Unfortunately, none of these software solutions meets all the requirements of the planner. Needless to say, each program contains only the product range of its manufacturer.

Required is a uniform, internationally standardised definition for product catalogue data interchange. Such a definition eliminates the need to manage different data formats and to use different software systems to deal with products of different manufacturers, and this leads to a significant reduction of costs for manufacturers and users. Integrating this data into BIM-systems (Building Information Modelling) allows data interchange between IT systems. In addition, to the benefit for planning, there will be an amount of advantages for other software solutions, e.g. facility management and life cycle management.

VDI 3805 is the German standard that addresses these objectives in Germany for decades. However this is an old standard that uses old technologies. Transforming it into an ISO standard, modernising it through the use of recent ISO or EU standards will extend its benefits to the whole European community.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

EN ISO 16757 focuses on the support of manufacturers to provide their product data in standardised electronic product catalogues. Part 1 (Concepts, Architecture and Model) and Part 2 (Geometry) have already been published by ISO TC 59/SC 13/WG 11.

To ensure that the implementation of these principles in Part 5 are in line with existing or emerging BIM standards, the project team of EN ISO 16757 has been working over the last three years in a number of standardisation projects mainly on CEN level. These standards form the basis for the modelling of product catalogues in EN ISO 16757:

- ▶ EN ISO 23386 (Building information modelling and other digital processes used in construction - Methodology to describe, author and maintain properties in interconnected data dictionaries)
- ▶ EN ISO 23387 (Building Information Modelling (BIM) - Data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of any built asset - Concepts and principles (ISO/DIS 23387:2019))
- ▶ EN 17549-2 (Building information modelling – Information structure based on EN ISO 16739-1:2020 to exchange data templates and data sheets for construction objects Part 2: Configurable construction objects and requirements)

These standards form the foundation on which EN ISO 16757 Part 5 will be built. They are now mature enough and contain important aspects which are required for the exchange of complex product catalogues. Therefore, now the time is ripe for starting the specification of the product catalogue exchange mechanisms.

As these underlying standards have been mainly developed by CEN TC 442, the ISO 16757 project team decided to develop Part 5 in CEN TC442 under Vienna agreement, instead of ISO TC 59/SC 13/WG 11.

EN ISO 16757 has been waiting for the publication of EN 17549-2 for many years. It will be the first standard based on it and EN ISO 23386 and EN ISO 12006-3. As such it is a bit experimental and may constitute a template for future standards.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

This standard will permit the development of HVAC product catalogues that are not dedicated to a single manufacturer but may include products from both large manufacturers or SMEs. Without such a standard, each manufacturer has to develop its own, proprietary, product catalogue, which represents a cost that an SME manufacturer cannot afford.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to developing EN ISO 16757-5.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

My fellowship will contribute to the preparation of the EN ISO 16757-5 formal draft. This fellowship ends on Nov 15, 2024 and the formal draft should be submitted to CEN and ISO beginning of 2025.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The draft document of EN ISO 16757 has been approved by CEN and ISO in June 2024. The current steps focus on collecting the comments to prepare the formal draft.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:1991542&cs=100E563A3950D53807585F6A443ACB202

Guidelines to create a Digital Product Passport (CWA)

Rembrandt Koppelaar

*Chairperson of the CWA, EcoWise Ekodenge Ltd
United Kingdom*

Sector

Circular Economy Including Digital Product Passport

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN JTC 24 Digital Product Passport

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The European Commission has set a key priority under the Green Deal in developing a novel system for product information transparency to consumers under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation adopted in May 2024. The majority of products sold on the EU market are to be equipped with Digital Product Passports by 2030, with requirements set in delegated acts per product category, so as to create a level playing field of information availability in relation to their environmental and circularity performance of products. Digital Product Passports also unlock non-mandatory possibilities for producing companies that include material and product traceability, information management & exchanges and circularity management,

The challenge is that at present there is no guidance for companies on how to design, implement and utilise a Digital Product Passport. Neither within a standardisation context or outside of official standards. There are preliminary discussions at EU Commission level on setting up a DPP implementation support centre. There is a Standardisation request by the EU Commission accepted by CEN/CENELEC that has resulted in JTC24 to implement 8 harmonised standards for the DPP system in support of the COM(2022) 142 final proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament.

The CWA under development supported by my fellowship addresses this gap by supporting companies and economic operators to design their DPP, enhance their IT systems, and implement new information exchange processes using the DPP, either directly or in communication with a 3rd party for procuring it as a service. The activity will enable the development of the CWA which will be widely disseminated as a pre-standard through clustering with EU funded projects focusing on Digital Product Passports (a list of over 20 such projects has been identified).

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The project contributes at two levels to ICT standards. First as a main outcome a CWA registered at CEN as CEN/WS 'Guidelines to create a Digital Product Passport –the EU project CircThread experience'. Second, detailed referencing of ICT standards in the CWA usable as building blocks for DPPs in their design and implementation choices. At present a screening is being undertaken including existing standards landscape mapping efforts from StandICT.eu, the CIRPASS-1 project, and CircThread project.

A first listing of related ICT standards to be referenced in the CWA:

- ▶ Product identification for Digital Product Passport setup (e.g. product model, batch, item level), ISO/IEC 15459-4:2014; ISO/IEC 15418:2016; ISO/IEC 9834-8; IEC 61406-1:2022; IEC 61406-2:2024; ISO-8000:115:2024; W3C DID v1.0.
- ▶ Data carrier standards, ISO/IEC 15415:2011; ISO/IEC 16022:2006; CEN/TR 16671:2014; ISO/IEC 18004:2015; ISO/IEC 15418:2016; EN 17071:2019; ISO/IEC 24731; ISO/IEC 20248:2022; EN IEC 61406-1:2022
- ▶ Labelling aspects and ICT manufacturing shop floor labelling integration ISO ISA-95 standards; ISO 22742:2010; ISO 28219:2017; ISO/IEC 22603-1&2.
- ▶ Information portal contents of the product, including also Circular & Environmental KPI selection options in line with EU regulations and related existing product information standards, EN ISO/TS 14027:2017, EN ISO 14020:2022 family; WBCSD PACT 2024; ISO/IEC DIS 82474:2024; ISO/DIS 59040:2023(E); ISO 59020:2024.Sector specific DPP category references (e.g. batches for construction products & BIM Objects); NBS BIM object standard; EN 17549-1; EN 17549-2.
- ▶ Digital security requirements for cloud based DPP services management, ISO/IEC 27001:2012; ITU-T X.1147; ITU-T X.1603; ITU-T X.1752.
- ▶ Digital Skills requirements to set up a DPP internally within a company or by a 3rd party following data process requirements, IEEE P7015.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The project contribution in terms of the CWA under development will support SMEs that want to or are required legally to have a DPP for their products, which is a majority of SMEs in Europe. Close to 30 product categories are expected to be mandated to have a DPP in the mid-term future. To ensure the CWA effort is impactful for SMEs consideration is made of CEN-CENELEC GUIDE 17: Guidance for writing standards taking into account SME needs (2010). The impact on these SMEs is expected in terms of accelerating their journey to develop and set up their Digital Product Passport. By providing a concise guidance document that has been developed as a CWA pre-standard for understanding the scope, context, potentials and design and implementation decisions for Digital product passports.

Impact on Society

The CWA will also benefit European society by supporting economic actors to understand how DPPs can support their activities by enabling new information generation mechanisms and sharing for a circular economy.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

The project will deliver a CEN Workshop Agreement, with as current title 'Guidelines to create a Digital Product Passport –the EU project CircThread experience', that is now under development with a kick-off meeting held on the 8th of July 2024. The CWA will be established at the end of 2024 with three further planned workshop meetings

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I lead the development of CEN CWA pre-standard and its current title is 'Guidelines to create a Digital Product Passport –the EU project CircThread experience.'

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The following activities are in progress:

- ▷ Screening of the landscape of ICT standards
- ▷ Drafting of the CWA text 1st version with a core writing team
- ▷ Liaison on specific questions and answers with committee members
- ▷ Preparation for the next CWA workshop meeting on the 3rd of September 2024.

The following activities are planned following CEN CWA procedures:

- ▷ Revision of the CWA text from committee contributions.
- ▷ Public commenting on the CWA text following the drafting process.
- ▷ Four further CWA workshop meetings.
- ▷ Publication of the finalised CWA guideline document.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-and-events/news/2024/workshop/2024-06-24-circthread/>

Adaptive and multiple output power supplies based on USB Type C connector and USB PD support

Cornelis J.M. Lanting

*Rapporteur / Editor, DATSA Belgium
Belgium*

Sector

ICT Environmental Impact

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI TC ATTM
ETSI TC ISG OEU

Role

Expert member and project editor

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With this fellowship, my priority is to support the EU Directive aimed at a unified charging connector and system for ICT and other equipment. The USB-C connector is a great step forward, but the complexity of the PD system is problematic for users, and the information provided by manufacturers on compliance with PD is often at least incomplete. Moreover, products on the market can be behind but also ahead of the technical requirements in the EU Directive. The PD extension to USB-C has ample possibilities, but is for users difficult to understand, incl. possible safety hazards (with up to 240 W, USB is no longer 'innocent' Also, the information provided by manufacturers on more complex power consuming devices such as smartphones, tablets and PCs is insufficient. The USB-C connector has the ability to challenge wired LAN connections to portable equipment.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In the framework of this fellowship, I contribute to the further development of the international standardisation framework complementing the existing standard EN IEC 62680-1-3:2021. This standard is technically sound, but as a standard not sufficient for users to understand the complex USB-C with PD interface that they have literally in their hands

This standardisation effort concerns several challenges that the standard implies. Notably, it is recognised that it is difficult to keep this standard synchronised with the latest specifications from the USB-IF. However, new products on the market follow (more or less) the latest USB-IF specifications.

Also, the information provided by manufacturers on the compliance with USB-IF specifications, and hence EN IEC 62680, is insufficient. Therefore, there is a need for additional information to be provided to users; this could be an issue to be addressed by the EC; it could be possible using an organisation to provide such information as a service on their behalf.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

These new standards impact directly SMEs and other organisations that are affected as users of ICT equipment. It can also benefit SMEs deploying the potential of the USB-C with PD power supplies and chargers available on the market. Also SMEs are able to introduce their own more intelligent and communicative power supplies and chargers

Impact on Society

Given the EU choice for the USB-C interface for charging and connection, it is now essential to make its use easy, successful and efficient, and reduce the risk of mismatch, unnecessary negative experiences and safety issues. A wide adoption will support the EU's initiative, and will increase the benefits beyond 'just' the Smartphone and Tablet domain, and enter the general rechargeable domain as the preferred standard.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute developing new work items (NWIP) within two ETSI TCs

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to two different technical reports in two ETSI technical committees, including ISG OEU and ATTМ. The latter is This deliverable is an extension to a series of ATTМ deliverables: 'Sustainable Digital Multiservice Communities (ATTМ); External Common Power Supply for Customer Premises Network and Access Equipment'

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The next steps for the two technical reports that I lead as editor are the initiation of the adoption process, for the TR in ETSI ISG OEU this shall be done in the end of September 2024 and for the TR in ETSI TC ATTМ in the end of October 2024, corresponding with the ending of this fellowship.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.etsi.org/committee/attm>

 <https://www.etsi.org/committee/oeu>

Contribution to new standard for autonomous robotic systems IEEE1872.3

João Manuel Leitão Quintas

*Coordinator of RTD at IPNIAs / Principal Researcher, Instituto Pedro Nunes
Portugal*

Sector

Robotics and Autonomous Systems

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEEE SA P 1872.3 REMAR - Ontology for reasoning on multiple autonomous robots
IEEE SA P1872.2 Autonomous Robotics (AuR) Ontology Working Group

Role

Expert member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship contributes to ongoing efforts related to standardisation on topics related to Robotics and Autonomous Systems and Artificial Intelligence.

My key objective is to contribute to the discussions and creation of resources that can support and facilitate the dissemination and adoption of standards, policy and guidelines proposed by key opinion leaders involved mainly in the recently created Working Group that is developing the standard project IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots (<https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1872.3/11037/>)

In the current state of the art, the implementation of standard ontologies in Robotics and Autonomous Systems is still considered a challenge but is considered necessary. One of the main challenges faced by current working groups is still how to provide a unified way of representing the underlying semantics and defining the vocabulary to be used by the system, thereby allowing precise knowledge transfer for problem-solving and unambiguous communications between heterogeneous, autonomous systems.

The EU Priorities & Gaps identified that will benefit from the work conducted include Sustainable Growth / Robotics and autonomous systems and Societal Challenges / eHealth, healthy living and ageing.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship enables me to carry out additional commitment and the effective contribution to the development and promoting adoption, of the IEEE P1872.3 standard, which is a logical extension to the IEEE 1872.2 and CORA ontology by defining additional ontologies appropriate for Autonomous Robotics (AuR).

This fellowship also enables me to bring knowledge and perspectives from the European RTD ecosystem related to robotics and automation but also with the application domain of ICT for Health and Active and Assisted Living. In particular, from the application perspective, it addresses “ICT for Healthcare” and “eHealth, healthy living and ageing”. This activity is expected to influence the preparation of a technology-oriented standard by sharing concerns

and requirements that may be relevant for future adoption of the standard in concrete solutions targeting these sectors.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

SMEs related to robotics and/or developing artificial agents with a certain degree of autonomy can be impacted by this contribution, as the standard being developed aims to bring added value for integration and interoperability in solutions based on robotic and autonomous systems.

Impact on Society

One of the direct impacts of my activity is widening the stakeholders' network that can also learn from the standard development and share domain-specific information that is relevant to implement use cases for the standard. It may be of particular interest to the TEF-Health European Project⁶, which is establishing a test and experimentation facilities network across the EU, and I am part of the team and IPN which is leading the Portuguese node.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

IEEE P1872.3 is a work in progress development of a new standard under IEEE Standard Association. Currently it has an active PAR (Project Authorization Request).

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

It will contribute to joint papers being prepared by my working group.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The PAR is currently undergoing its development stage until December 2026. The WG is conducting monthly meetings combined with work sessions every two weeks to discuss different aspects of the standard and finding opportunities for joint collaboration that ultimately contribute as evidence to support the future adoption of the standard.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://sagroups.ieee.org/1872-2/>

6 <https://www.tefhealth.eu/>

Representation of domain-specific concepts in digital twins and other technical information assets

Sabine Mahr

Consultant; word b sign Sabine Mahr
Germany

Sector

Digitisation Of European Industry

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 37 Language and terminology WG 10 Technical communication

IEC/TC 3/JWG 16 Maintenance of ISO/IEC 82079 standards series

CEN/CLC JTC 24 Digital Product Passport (DPP)

ISO/TC 37/SC 3/WGs 1, 3, and 5, Data categories, Data interchange, Terminology extraction

IEC/ TC 3/WG 27 Terminology

Role

Expert member and project leader to ISO 24183:2024, Technical communication – Vocabulary (published 2024-01)

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Semantic interoperability is key to industrial automation and state-of-the-art product development, where digital representations of processes, products and their components, i.e., their digital twins called Asset Administration Shells (AASs), interact with each other. In product development, this is a necessity with regards to simulation in early stages, as well as with the Digital Product Passport (DPP), which needs to be made available for an ever-increasing number of products throughout almost all industries.

To facilitate interoperability between digital representations of products (and product components), the underlying concepts of a product schema, model or ontology require proper definitions of their interrelations and characteristics, as well as unique identifiers to make them accessible. The same holds true for “technical documentation” as an integral part of the product. Its standardized metadata are currently being introduced into a submodel template “Intelligent information for use”. Determining such concept systems and assigning unique identifiers to its concepts is exactly what modern terminology work has been concerned with over the last 100 years. In the industrial automation domain, this endeavour is realized by means of concept repositories that inform the submodel templates of its AASs.

To date, terminologists and engineers have been working in rather separated environments, while conceptual modeling has become increasingly important in both worlds, esp. when Industry 4.0 with its digital assets is concerned. Engineers can learn from terminologists how to properly define concepts and their interrelations. This is needed for establishing concept repositories, like controlled vocabularies such as the CDD, which form the backbone of the AAS. Terminologists, on the other hand, have long been regarded to be performing academic rather than practical work. They can now contribute to digitalized

industry scenarios by providing concept models for I4.0 assets within a company or industry. Technical communicators work at the intersection of both professions, which means they are predestined to serve as mediators between the two professions.

The NWIP I plan to submit, “Technical communication – Representation of conceptual information in information products”, aims at providing technical communicators and information architects with some general principles and a framework of guidelines on how to define a style guide for the proper application of conceptual information in technical communication. Conceptual information is an information type that has long been neglected in favour of the task-oriented instructional information with its step-by-step procedure description. It helps building mental models in human brains as well as machine-readable ontologies.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In the framework of this fellowship, I contribute to several standardisation projects, including:

- ▶ IEC/IEEE 82079-1, *Preparation of information for use (instructions for use) of products – Part 1: Principles and general requirements*: This standard is currently under revision. Its 3rd edition will take more into account digitalization, in elaborating on the wide variety of format, media and (multi-)modal resources that are now available. It will also talk about information for use as the digital twin of “technical documentation”, a digital representation in its own right.
- ▶ IEC PAS 63485, *Intelligent Information Request and Delivery – A process model for the exchange of information for use*, represents the above-mentioned technical communication metadata standard.
- ▶ IEC 63278 series, *Asset Administration Shell for industrial applications*: Information for use, esp. of the conceptual information type, can serve as a concept repository referenced by AAS submodel templates and submodels (see Fig. 4 in IEC 63278-1)
- ▶ CEN/CLC / JTC 24 Digital Product Passport (DPP) NWIPs: In this context, information for use represents a resource interlinked with sustainability information
- ▶ IEC 61360 series on Common Data Dictionary (CDD): In the long run, information for use related to specific domains should be inserted as new entries to the CDD.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

A Digital Product Passport (DPP) will be required for almost any physical product, starting in 2026 for some product groups and then subsequently widening its application range. This means that all manufacturers are required to provide various sustainability-related data on their products, once they enter the European market.

With the advent of the DPP, technical communication will most probably either be part of the DPP or strongly intertwined with the information provided through it. Technical communicators who are capable of providing product information arranged into a machine-readable concept model of the product and its context of use are in high demand on the labour market and in the freelance consultant market. Approaching the modeling task in accordance with the principles that will be laid out in the NWIP will help them to perform their work more easily and in a well-structured manner.

Impact on Society

The information chunks that convey conceptual information will conform to the “Intelligent information for use” metadata scheme, so that they provide meta-information about their semantics and hence become machine-readable and semantically interoperable with other information, e.g., in other submodels of the AAS. Which is, on the other hand, a prerequisite for their accessibility via differing sensory modalities in humans and therefore for barrier-free communication. This aspect has gained in importance with the imminent entry into force of the European Accessibility Act in June 2025.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Not yet, as my fellowship is still running. The mentioned NWIP is under preparation and will be submitted to ISO/TC 37 for approval in December 2024, after the next meeting of the national mirror committee, national acceptance provided.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I will contribute to drafting technical documents related to the mentioned standardisation projects.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Possible future activities are manifold. The NWIP I propose could also gain importance in SMART standardization projects, whose main challenge is semantic interoperability.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.researchgate.net/publication/376566701_The_impact_of_ISOTC_37_standards_on_technical_communication

■ Lifts and Escalators in Smart Cities

Gero Gschwendtner

Prof. Mechanical Engineering (HTL St. Pölten) and Independent Consultant

Austria

Sector

Smart Cities

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 178 Lifts, escalators and moving walks
ISO/TC 178/ WG 4 Safety requirements and risk assessment
ISO/TC 178/ WG 5 Escalators and moving walks
ISO/TC 178/ WG 6 Lift installation
CEN/TC 10 Lifts, escalators and moving walks
CEN/TC 10/WG 2 Escalators and moving walks
Joint Working Group (JWG) CEN/ TC 10 + SESA + SAC/ TC 196 +
ON AG 017 Aufzüge und Fahrtreppen
ON AG 017.02 Fahrtreppen und Fahrsteige
Global Technical Advisory Group of WEEF (World Elevator and Escalator Federation)

Role

Chair of ISO/TC178

Convenor of CEN/TC10/WG 2 Escalators and moving walks

Expert member in the other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Until 2022 the lift and escalator sector lacked any specific ICT standard, except for the cybersecurity standard. Initially, the philosophy driving the standardisation efforts within ISO/CEN was to incorporate all subjects into the core product standards, referred to as the “product bible” ISO 8100-1/2 and EN 115-1 (in the process to be published as 1:1 as ISO 8103-1; approved as a NWI 20.07.2023 and currently ballot ongoing for skipping circulation of CD draft and move project directly to DIS stage). Over the years, as specific topics grew increasingly complex, supplementary standards were developed to support the main product standards.

It became evident that ICT was lacking in comprehensive coverage, given its rapid advancement. Consequently, a decision was made to analyse this situation, formulate a future strategy, address this issue, and bridge the gap. The creation of these new standards and technical specifications is of utmost priority.

Simultaneously, the main product standards (referred to as the “product bible”) must be maintained, and certain general ICT aspects need to be incorporated within them.

Furthermore, a significant challenge faced by ISO/TC 178 and the entire lifts and escalator sector pertains to the ongoing situation in China. Currently, China is undertaking several local standardisation projects at a notably rapid pace. Their release process involves fewer parties and is considerably faster than the CEN and ISO process. This underscores the utmost importance of ensuring that SAC continues its active participation in ISO and takes over all ISO standards as local standards. Consequently, additional corporations have been established,

and regular exchange meetings are being conducted to exert the greatest possible influence in this matter.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Lifts, escalators and moving walks are essential elements in providing safe access to buildings. There is a strong emphasis on safety, accessibility, energy & environment and highly relevant for the future ISO/TC 178 activities are also focusing now to a strong extent on ICT.

ISO/TC 178/WG 12 “Cybersecurity” was found in 2019. Within 3 years they published the new ISO 8102-20 Electrical requirements for lifts, escalators and moving walks - Part 20: Cybersecurity. To ensure that this standard can be used to meet the relevant EU regulation, it was decided in the April ISO/TC Plenary meeting to revise this standard.

WG 12 is now working on ISO TS 8102-21 “On-site and Off-site software updates” for lifts and escalators. This project just moved to stage 30.20 where the CD draft has been finished and CD consultation was initiated 13.09.2024.

In addition, ISO/TC 178/WG 13 “New Technologies” have been found end 2022 as a result of the work initiated by ISO/TC 178/AHG1 in 2019.

After the successful drafting of ISO/WD TS 8100-10 “Lifts for the transport of persons and goods — Part 10: Building Information Modelling” this project just moved to stage 30.20 where the CD draft has been finished and CD consultation was initiated 10.09.2024.

Also, in the April ISO/TC Plenary it was also decided to start the new project ISO/NP TS 8100-11, Lifts for the transport of persons and goods — Part 11: Interoperability between lift and other systems. The NP ballot just closed and awaiting the results.

Finally, the ongoing work for the lift and escalator product standards (“product bibles”, which ensure the implementation of the ICT standards), energy standards and risk analysis standard are continuing, where the current focus is on the following standards:

ISO/WD 8100-1, ISO/WD 8100-2, ISO/PWI 14798-1, ISO/PWI TR 14798-2, ISO 8103-1, EN-115-1.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

ISO/TC 178 has a liaison to:

- ▶ ELA European Lift Association
- ▶ SBS - Small Business Standards with EFESME (European Federation for Elevator Small and Medium-sized Enterprises aisbl) as an expert member for lifts.

Both associations are highly interested in this topic and with this liaison they participate actively at the ISO/TC 178 meetings as well as at the relevant WG meetings.

Chairing the meeting and giving them also relevant time in the meetings to talk and bring up their issues is essential for them; this is under my responsibility and highly considered, even several “big companies” are sometimes not so happy with this approach.

Impact on Society

Lifts, escalators and moving walks are essential elements for the transportation of society. With this work safe access and accessibility for all is provided. Furthermore, this work encompasses energy efficiency and adherence to the United Nations' sustainability goals namely 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, and 13 which are integral components of the standards.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, in my roles as chair, convener and expert member in several working groups, I contribute to developing new standards as well as revising existing ones.

In the framework of this fellowship, I have contribute to the following new standards:

- ▶ ISO/CD TS 8100-10: Stage 30.20

- ▷ ISO/CD TS 8102-21: Stage 30.20
- ▷ ISO/DIS 8103-1: Stage 60.00
- ▷ ISO/NP TS 8100-11 Stage 10.60 Awaiting results of NP ballot:

In parallel, I am working on the revision of the following standards :

- ▷ ISO/DIS 8100-1/2: Stage 40.60: Resolving DIS comments + Awaiting final report of voting
- ▷ ISO/PWI 14798-1 & ISO/PWI TR 14798-2 PWI with ongoing work:
- ▷ ISO/AWI 8102-20: Stage 20.00 process started since September .2024

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Related to the standardisation projects listed here above, I contribute to drafting both, technical reports and technical specifications.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

As seen in the list of standards/technical specifications, all of them are in progress (but also regularly submitted to the different voting stages).

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/53970.html

 www.standict.eu/success-stories/standardising-ict-lifts-escalators-and-moving-walks

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